

Deliverable D3.4 – Open Peer Review: Good practices and lessons learned

OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results

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Abbreviations

EU – European Union

DMP - data management plan

DMAIC - methodology cycle including Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve and Control phases

SWOT – analysis including Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

HMD – Human Mortality Database

OPR – open peer review

OS – open science

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Summary

Project OpenUP aims to provide a map of scholarly peer review systems including the examination of currently available tools and services and outlining the developments in the field. Besides providing an overview of peer review alternatives, the main purpose of the present study is to identify the missing elements and the challenges researchers face in the publishing and evaluation processes. The results of this study contribute to the guidelines and recommendations the project prepares for decision makers on the implementation of alternative peer review methodologies. The ultimate goal is to increase the uptake of open peer review (OPR). To this end, on the one hand, researchers need (1) incentives to participate in alternative scholarly communication processes and (2) easy-to-use infrastructures to comply with open science related EU and national mandates and guidelines. On the other hand, publishers need to offer OPR as part of the publication process. By collecting good examples of OPR initiatives within the current scholarly communication discourse, this study urges the introduction of future pilot studies that implement OPR practices both on EU and national levels in order to raise awareness and increase skills among researchers on open science (OS) practices.

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim and scope

Open peer review is gaining a momentum in the transforming scholarly publishing discourse and plays a pivotal role in the process of transitioning academic publishing into a more transparent system. Peer review is one of the founding pillars of scholarly publishing to ensure the reliability and validity of research. As open access has become more widely accepted method of dissemination, peer review provided the trust in new publishing models. The growth of science and the alternative publishing practices highlighted the problems of the established journal based peer review process. The new practices have given way to more transparent review methods and tools, which in return have become subject of public scrutiny. Good examples of effective implementation of alternative techniques encourage the different research communities to consider and implement practices that are aligned with the main principles of open scholarship.

Open scholarship, discussed by Knowledge Exchange, refers to a variety of initiatives with the primary aim to make research more inclusive, more accessible, more networked, and more effective. Open scholarship is complex notion, it is more of an umbrella term. Differences in language and research methodologies, differences in requirements by funders and publishers, all lead to inconsistencies how openness is defined and implemented in research practices (Knowledge Exchange, 2017).

Open scholarship is a complex ecosystem where processes of scientific research and communication are closely interrelated. Therefore, the benefits of transparency are only fully realized when a critical mass of stakeholders are engaged and open processes and infrastructures are in place to support them. Segregated, individual efforts may not have the same benefits, as interlinked processes. Research and communication practices of communities with various geographical, organisational and disciplinary cultures interpret transparency and openness in many ways, thus the challenge for open scholars is to find a common thread among all these different realisations of open scholarship.

The current study (D3.4) has the primary aim to show some of these good practices of open communication conduct which can pave the way to open peer review across research cultures. The main purposes it strives to achieve include: (1) updating the landscape scan results put forward in D3.1, and (2) validating the desk research analysis through pilot studies and workshops. Therefore, D3.4 is basically a summary of several different micro studies executed to map out practical implementations of open peer review tools and methodologies.

1.2 Methodology

In D3.1 a life cycle approach was introduced as an effective methodology to manage the continuously changing peer review discourse. This approach is proved to be beneficial for several reasons:

- the changing publishing discourse is broken down to individual processes as points of intervention,
- the analysis of activities at each phase clearly defines the problems and barriers the new practices have to overcome,
- the methodology guarantees a continuous check of involved issues,
- it provides a framework for the study starting from providing a landscape scan of peer review methods and alternative solutions (D3.1), defining the problems, to providing good examples and recommendations on how the new peer review approaches can be introduced in different fields of study (D3.4).

Figure 1. DMAIC Methodology. Source: Six Sigma, Villanova University¹

The DMAIC methodology (see Figure 1) is a process-centered life cycle with the primary purpose of identifying the root causes of problems in a given process and providing solution recommendations for improvements (Borror, 2009). This methodology serves a dual purpose here: (1) the framework of DMAIC structures the analysis process, and (2) the landscape scan is understood as a broadened process of mapping the existing peer review methods and analyzing/categorizing the emerging alternative methods/tools. This analysis informs the basis for recommending policy directions to integrate the new services into the current scholarly communication system.

Applied to the over study on open peer review, the phases entail:

Define phase: context of research is explained (D3.1) including

- providing a landscape scan of alternative peer review tools and methodologies,
- explanation of the primary concepts, which provide the basis for the current research on alternative review methods and tools, including the definition of open science, peer review and open peer review, and
- establishing ties to other projects on open science, such as FOSTER through the definition of open science and OpenAIRE through the definition of open peer review.

Measure phase: current practices are examined (D3.1) including

- gathering data to identify types of problems in the current publishing system, and
- collecting feedback from stakeholders (user-centered surveys conducted within the project OpenAIRE in 2016 and OpenUP in 2017, methodology and results are discussed in Chapter 2.2).

¹ <https://www.villanovau.com/resources/six-sigma/six-sigma-methodology-dmaic/#.WOTfKfnyjcs>

Analyze phase: conducting gap analysis and landscape scan (D3.1) including

- identifying gaps through a SWOT analysis,
- setting up categories of alternative peer methods and services,
- the description of the alternative review tools based on OpenAIRE's definition of open peer review.

Improve phase: implications of open peer review (OPR) (D3.4) including:

- identifying good examples for alternative review methodologies,
- establishing the missing elements based on feedbacks from stakeholders (expert workshop on peer review and OPR was conducted in March 2018, which was attended by 14 experts, results are discussed in Chapter 4.1 and 4.2),
- providing examples for implementation of review and related practices (an OpenUP and FOSTER joined training workshop was conducted in June 2018, results are discussed in Chapter 4.3.2),
- collecting policy recommendations and guidelines for future developments in the field.

(Control phase): to manage and sustain changes over time.

This report focuses on the fourth phase of the DMAIC methodology cycle. The primary objective of the study is to interpret the implications of alternative peer review methods and tools available for researchers who seek other review options than the established publishing system can offer. One of the project's ultimate objective is to provide a set of validated practical policy and implementation recommendations and guidelines for EU, national and institutional policymakers. These recommendations will be a valuable tool in supporting decision makers to evaluate needs for and prioritization of supportive actions for advancing a more open and gender-sensitive science system. The *Improve* phase investigates how current alternative practices and the present and future implementation of open science policies will affect uptake of open peer review among various research communities.

The *Control* phase of Open Peer Review will be considered as a Key Result Area for D2.4 Updated Exploitation and Sustainability Plan. Future projects and initiatives should continue the analysis set up within project OpenUP and examine on the one hand, the uptake of alternative evaluation methods in various disciplinary and geographical cultures, and on the other hand, identify the problems within the implementation processes, leading the analysis back to the first *Define* phase of the methodology.

The study is built on results of several different analysis and reports created on the transforming peer review discourse. It is a revision of D3.1 (Görögh, 2017), which was meant to provide a landscape scan of the present situation of scholarly evaluation systems and emerging alternative review solutions. Therefore, the current analysis uses the results from the previous analysis and supplements them with results obtained during the past year (June 2017-June 2018).

Within the framework of this study, the scholarly peer review system is investigated in various contexts (review of publications, research data in social sciences and humanities, review of conferences) and from various perspectives (researchers, publishers, funders).

The study is based on various methods to collect and analyze data. The desk research continued within the second phase of the project execution is supplemented by interviews and workshops results conducted in various tasks of the project work packages (T3.3, T3.4, Pilot studies 1, 2, 3).

2. Context of research

2.1 What is open peer review?

As an integral part of our work package, Deliverable 3.3 -Application framework and transformation scenarios for open peer review²- set the context of the OPR research for the project. Informally, peer review is just the development of nascent ideas and theories through critical discussion with others. As such it is as old as knowledge creation itself. Its stricter sense – the formal scholarly publishing process where an editor sends copies of a manuscript to people judged knowledgeable enough to be able to comment on its suitability for publication – is more recent. In this mode it has been the default of academic publishing only since the mid-20th century.

Peer review serves to validate the soundness, substance and originality of a work, or to help improve it until it meets required standards for these criteria. Peer review, in its current form, is typically:

- **Anonymous** – either the author doesn't know who the reviewer is (single-blind) or author and reviewer are unknown to each other (double-blind).
- **Hidden** – the process takes place behind closed doors (or, rather, password privileges) and reviews are not published.
- **Selective** – reviewers are chosen by the editor.

Studies have shown that although academics are, on the whole, fairly content with peer review, they think it could work better^{3, 4, 5}. Problems include:

- **Time** – peer review often takes a long, long time. Could open review help speed up the process?
- **Accountability** – the anonymity of reviewing, although in principle meritocratic (as junior researchers can criticise the work of luminaries without fear of reprisals), also makes it unaccountable (some say Kafkaesque). Should professionals cast judgements in secret? Shouldn't they be prepared to stand openly by what they believe? Relatedly, would reviews conducted in public be more constructive and less confrontational?
- **Bias** – given the specialised nature of academia, a researcher's nearest "peers" will often be known to them as either friends or rivals. This fact naturally leads to concern that rejection or acceptance might sometimes have social, rather than scientific, grounds. Even where authors' names are withheld, it is often clear from the research itself (or a cursory Google) who the author is. If reviews were public, such biases might be further suppressed.
- **Scams** – that the peer process takes place behind closed doors also likely aids peer review scams in avoiding detection.
- **Incentive** – reviewing, done well, is hard work. If reviews were open, busy academics and researchers could take credit for them, demonstrating experience, community involvement, and impact.
- **Wasted effort** – reviewer comments often add context or point to areas for future work. Reviewer disagreements can expose areas of tension in a theory or argument. Readers may find such information helpful and yet, at present, this potentially valuable additional information is wasted. Furthermore, as

² Ross-Hellauer, T. (2018)

³ <http://www.publishingresearch.org.uk/documents/PRCsummary4Warefinal.pdf>

⁴ <http://dx.doi.org/10.1087/20150104>

⁵ <http://editorsupdate.elsevier.com/issue-45-november-2014/researchers-think-peer-review-process/>

rejected papers are usually resubmitted elsewhere (to be reviewed all over again), there is a duplication of effort – the same paper might be reviewed multiple times.

As the open science agenda has taken hold, “open peer review” (OPR) has been proposed as a solution to some of these problems. By bringing peer review into line with the goals of open science, proponents aim to bring greater transparency, flexibility, inclusivity and/or accountability to the process. Various innovative publishers, including F1000, BioMed Central, PeerJ, and Copernicus Publications, already implement systems that identify themselves as OPR. However, such systems differ widely across publishers, and OPR has neither a standardised definition nor an agreed schema of its features and implementations.

While the term is used by some to refer to peer review where the identities of both author and reviewer are disclosed to each other, for others it signifies systems where reviewer reports are published alongside articles. For others it signifies both of these conditions, and for yet others it describes systems where not only “invited experts” are able to comment. For still others, it includes a variety of combinations of these and other novel methods. These differing flavours of OPR include independent factors (open identities, open reports, open participation, etc.) which usually have no necessary connection to each other, and very different benefits and drawbacks. Evaluation of the efficacy of these differing variables and hence comparison between differing systems can be problematic as it is often unclear which distinct configuration of OPR is under discussion.

To bring clarity to how the term is used, in 2017 Ross-Hellauer systematically analysed definitions of OPR in the literature to identifying seven core traits:

- **Open identities** – authors and reviewers are aware of each other’s identity.
- **Open reports** – review reports are published alongside the relevant article.
- **Open participation** – the wider community are able to contribute to the review process.
- **Open interaction** – direct reciprocal discussion between author(s) and reviewers, and/or between reviewers, is allowed and encouraged.
- **Open pre-review manuscripts** – manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g. via preprint servers like arXiv) in advance of formal peer review procedures.
- **Open final-version commenting** – review or commenting on final “version of record” publications.
- **Open platforms (“decoupled review”)** – review is facilitated by a different organisational entity than the venue of publication.

That review found a total of 22 unique configurations of these traits amongst the various definitions (i.e. 22 distinct definitions of OPR in the reviewed literature). Across all definitions, the core elements were open identities and open reports, with one or both elements present in over 95% of definitions. Among the other elements, open participation was the next most common element, and should perhaps be considered a core trait in the social sciences and humanities (where it appeared in more than 50% of definitions). Further secondary elements are open interaction and open pre-review manuscripts. Fringe elements include open final version commenting and open platforms. (Figure 2)

That analysis mapped each of these traits to the perceived deficiencies in peer review that they were claimed to address, noting that “no individual trait addresses all of these problems, and that sometimes their aims may be in conflict”. It also reviewed the evidence for these claims, finding that in general “there is often little evidence to support or refute many of these claims”.

necessitating more back and forth between reviewers and authors, and more editorial mediation—might lead to longer reviewing times.

- **Lack of accountability and risks of subversion:** *Open identities* and *reports* can increase accountability through increased transparency and by making any conflicts of interest more immediately apparent to authors and future readers. *Open participation* could overcome problems associated with editorial selection of reviewers (e.g. biases, closed-networks, elitism). However, in opening up participation to the wider community, it might actually increase engagement by those with conflicts of interest. Where anonymity is possible, this may be particularly problematic. Moreover, lack of anonymity for reviewers in *open identities* review might subvert the process by discouraging reviewers from making strong criticisms, especially against higher-status colleagues.
- **Social and publication biases:** *Open reports* adds another layer of quality assurance, allowing the wider community to scrutinize reviews to examine decision-making processes. However, *open identities* removes anonymity conditions for reviewers (single-blind) or authors and reviewers (double-blind) which are traditionally in place to counteract social biases (although there is not strong-evidence that such anonymity has been effective).
- **Lack of incentives:** *Open reports* linked to *open identities* enable higher visibility for peer review activities, allowing review work to be cited in other publications and in career development activities linked to promotion and tenure. *Open participation* could in principle increase incentives to peer review by enabling reviewers to themselves select the works that they consider themselves qualified to judge; in practice, however, experience to date suggests that reviewers are less likely to review under this condition.
- **Wastefulness:** *Open reports* make currently invisible but potentially useful scholarly information available for re-use, as well as providing young researchers a guide (to tone, length, the formulation of criticisms) to help them as they begin to do peer review themselves.

These innovative solutions cannot be considered a general cure for the problems of the established review processes. They can be viewed as a toolbox to work with. Disciplinary differences, differences in publishing practices, funding and mandate requirements all should be taken into consideration when implementation of new peer review systems is being discussed. The needs and preferences of research communities will guide the direction of change.

2.2 Attitudes towards open peer review

Inconsistence is a characteristic of the transforming peer review discourse. But, there is one common element among the vast variety of attributes and methodologies of peer review alternatives: they strive to offer quality reviews. Open peer review is an integral part of the transforming publishing system. As open access publishing is moving mainstream, more attention is paid to the new tools in peer review, which accompany the alternative publishing processes.⁶ We have already established that peer review in general, regardless of the publishing venue it is coupled with, has its inherent problems (D3.1) which should be addressed in their own regard (bias, language).

Opinions greatly vary about the new methods and tools, this primary due to the fact that open peer review carries some dualities within the process: balancing transparency with professionalism or efficiency (time aspect) with

⁶ Ross-Hellauer, T. (2018)

adequacy (quality aspect) (Nguyen, 2015). Results of two stakeholder surveys, conducted by the OpenUP and OpenAIRE projects, demonstrate the attitudes toward the different attributes of openness:

OpenUP survey (2017), (Görögh, et al., 2017): The OpenUP survey was conducted between 20 January and 23 February 2017 with an aim to capture current perceptions and practices in peer review, dissemination of research results and impact measurement among European researchers. It was implemented via online survey and directly targeted to mined contact details of the main authors of publications stored in arXiv, Pubmed and RePEc. The survey received 1347 responses, of which 976 were completed.

On peer review, the OpenUP survey found that when asked their preferences for review of their own research outputs between more open peer review or the established peer review process, in some categories there was no unanimous preference among the researchers. For instance, 42% of the researchers preferred open participation (when a wider community of the researchers contribute to peer review) and 41% supported closed participation (only appointed peer reviewers contribute to peer review). Also, small differences were noted among the researchers who ‘strongly supported’ or ‘supported’ open report (review report is published alongside the relevant article), and closed report (no review report is published alongside the relevant article), and who assigned open pre-review (manuscripts are made available to researchers/public before formal peer review), and ‘no open pre-review’ (manuscripts are not made available to researchers/public before formal peer review) to the same categories. Nevertheless, the majority of researchers expressed similar opinions on some aspects of peer review. There were nearly 30% more respondents, who preferred closed identity (when neither the author’s nor the reviewer’s identity are disclosed) than open identity (59% versus 29%). Female researchers supported open identity over closed identity more than male researchers (i.e. 35% versus 26%). On the other hand, female scientists were much less in favour of open pre-review (33% versus 51%). More than half of the survey respondents showed strong support for open final version commenting (54% in favour of open final-version commenting versus 27% in favour of established practices) and more than two thirds supported open data review compared to no data review along with the paper (71% versus 14%).

Figure 3. Proportions of respondents attributing their support to different peer-review approaches. Source: Görögh, E. et al. (2017). Deliverable D3.1– Practices, evaluation and mapping: Methods, tools and user needs. OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results

OpenAIRE survey (2016) (Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B., 2017): OpenAIRE conducted an online survey during September and October 2016, which received a total of 3062 complete responses (a further 635 responses were discarded as incomplete). Of all respondents, when asked about their roles in scholarly communication (multiple choices were allowed, on average about 2.4 options were selected) 2923 as author (95.5%), 2681 as reviewer (87.6%), 1326 had acted as editor (43.3%), 137 as publisher (4.5%), and 92 in other roles (3%). The full survey results, recently published in PLOS One, show the majority of respondents to be in favour of OPR becoming mainstream scholarly practice, as is the case for other open science practices, like open access and open data. We also observed surprisingly high levels of experience with OPR, with three out of four (76.2%) respondents reporting having taken part in an OPR process as an author, reviewer, or editor. There were also high levels of support for most traits of OPR, particularly open interaction, open reports, and final-version commenting. Respondents were against opening reviewer identities to authors, however, with more than half believing it would make peer review worse. Overall the satisfaction with the peer review system used by scholarly journals seems to significantly vary across disciplines.

Figure 4. Will XXXX make peer review better, worse, or have no effect? Source: Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., Schmidt, B. (2017) “Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers“. PLOS ONE. CC BY 4.0

Taken together, these findings are very encouraging for OPR’s prospects of moving mainstream but further indicate that due care must be taken to avoid a “one-size-fits-all” solution and to tailor such systems to differing (especially disciplinary) contexts. They also show clearly that more research is needed. OPR is an evolving phenomenon and hence future studies are to be encouraged, especially to further explore differences between disciplines and monitor the evolution of attitudes.

There is hence an urgent need to offer further clarity on OPR, guidelines for effective implementation to foster innovation, and a need for publishers and researchers interested in OPR to come together to share data and scientifically explore the efficacy of OPR systems as part of an Open Peer Review Assessment Framework.

3. Current practices

3.1 Peer review processes in scholarly communication

Innovation has become an association with the peer review process in the past few years by the academics and new open publishers. Trends in innovative review methodologies center around several key issues: (1) increasing transparency and openness, (2) raising interaction and collaboration among stakeholders, and (3) ensuring a more proactive role and control to authors and reviewers.

The emergence of these new evaluation alternatives is definitely tied to the transforming scholarly communication system. Numerous new services and innovative platforms have now emerged that are attempting to disrupt the established peer review process (Tennant, 2017).

Figure 5. A brief timeline of the evolution of peer review. Source: Tennant JP, Dugan JM, Graziotin D *et al.* A multi-disciplinary perspective on emergent and future innovations in peer review [version 3; referees: 2 approved]. *F1000Research* 2017, **6**:1151 (doi: 10.12688/f1000research.12037.3)

The following section of the report describes initiatives and services of peer review alternatives, which are offered by established and open access publishers.

3.1.1 Publishers and publishing platforms

Frontiers

Frontiers is an established open access scholarly publisher with the aims to improve how science is reviewed, published, evaluated and disseminated to both researchers and the public. Founded in 2007, it has grown to become an impactful academic publisher with over 90,000 leading researchers on the editorial boards.

Its Collaborative Review Forum unites authors, reviewers, associate editors, and chief editors in a direct online dialogue, enabling quick iterations and facilitating consensus. It consists of two phases:

- **Independent Review:** during the Independent Review phase, the reviewers assess the manuscript independently from each other and from the authors, according to a standardized review template. These templates are adapted to each article type.
- **Interactive Review:** during the Interactive Review phase, authors and reviewers can interact with each other through real-time comments in the discussion forum. The Associate Editor and, if required, the Specialty Chief Editor can also enter the Review Forum and oversee the review process.

Frontiers provides a review template to make reviews systematic and convene the efforts of reviewers exclusively on objective issues. This helps focus the review on the quality of both the research and the manuscript. It also facilitates constructive comments to bring the final paper to its final format.

The identities of reviewers remain anonymous during the review period. When a manuscript is accepted for publication, the names of the reviewers who endorsed its publication appear on the published article, without exceptions. If a reviewer recommends rejection or withdraws during any stage of this process, his/her name will not be disclosed. Handling editors' names are also made public on the published article, acknowledging their contribution.

As a result of this process, reviews are conducted constructively, with editors and reviewers holding a level of accountability and responsibility for the paper by providing rigorous feedback that delivers the highest possible quality publication. It uses a single-blind peer review process where the author's identity is known to the reviewers.

Frontiers' publishing platform is custom developed. It guides authors, reviewers and editors through the review process. It generates alerts when an action is required. This ensures the average time from submission to final decision to 90 days.

Elsevier

Elsevier is a significant stakeholder in scholarly publishing. Although the majority of Elsevier journals use the traditional (single, double-blind) review process, the publisher started experiments with more transparent evaluation methodologies. Elsevier has been running a pilot for 3 years from 2012-2015. Within this experiment the review reports were freely accessible to all⁷. Each review report was assigned a separate DOI and they were grouped together on an annual basis and appeared in a separate issue of the participating journal (Mehmani, 2015).

The reviewers, upon receiving review invitation letter, are informed that what they are writing will be accessible without revisions. Reviewers can choose to stay anonymous or reveal their identity. The pilot included two OA journals and three subscription journals where reports were all available.

Elsevier is working on system improvements and innovations around peer review. They launched the Elsevier Reviewer Recognition platform in 2014 with the aim to support and recognize review work. The platform provides participating reviewers with a personalized profile page where their reviewing history is documented. The reviewer status is awarded based on the number of reviews they have completed for a specific journal (Prechelt, 2014). Results from the pilot study show that reviewer engagement is better enhanced by increased willingness and decreased time to review and improving transparency of the processes (Mehmani, 2016) (Tancock, 2018). Currently studies are conducted on the impact of the pilot on reviewer behaviour, regarding the speed of the peer review process, the decision of acceptance and the level of helpfulness of their reports and the acceptance rate to review. Authors and editors were also surveyed to find out about the impact of this experiment

⁷ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016819231630106X>

on their behaviour (Mehmani, 2017). Results of this survey show that editors notice the reports to be more in depth and constructive for authors, and authors are supportive of publication of their referee reports alongside their articles.

BMJ

BMJ Open is also investing in open peer review by publishing all reports and authors responses and granting a more active role to the authors and urging communication among authors, editors and reviewers. Within the transformed peer review process at BMJ Open, all articles are sent for external, open peer review. Responsibilities are shifted in this process, on the one hand from the reviewers, as they are not asked to judge importance or breadth of appeal of the manuscript, and to the authors, on the other hand, as they are asked to consult the journal's instructions for reviewers to ensure that the submission is complete. Upon publication, all previous versions of the manuscript are made available, as will the reviewers' comments and authors' replies to those comments.

BMJ Open also added post-publication peer review via the Disqus comments⁸ providing opportunity for the readers for rapid responses, rating the article positively or negatively and for article level metrics. Furthermore, the journal has a system built in to manage appeals on rejected manuscripts. The author has to provide a detailed response to all points raised by the reviewers and editors, ultimately stirring conversation among the stakeholders of the review process⁹.

eLife

eLife started experimenting with alternative peer review in 2012 (King, 2017). The journal's Editor-in-Chief Randy Schekman devised an approach to peer review in which editors and reviewers discuss the scientific merits of the manuscripts submitted before reaching a decision. The consultation among reviewers and editors start after all the reviews have been received with the aim of identifying essential revisions and resolving conflicting statements. A crucial part of the consultation process is open identities: the identity of everyone taking part is shared.

Now eLife is taking the transformation of the peer review system one step further by launching a trial to test the feasibility of a radical form of peer review (Patterson, 2018). The new peer review process transfers a greater responsibility to the author in the actual publishing workflow. After the editor has invited a manuscript for full peer review, the journal is committed to publishing the work along with the reviewer reports, the decision letter, and the author response. The actual peer review process includes a consultation amongst the referees, the results of which is communicated to the author by the editor in a consolidated decision letter. The authors response to this letter, alongside with all other correspondence including the review reports and the decision letter, is published with the revised manuscript. This approach actually combines several attributes of open peer review: open identities, open report, open interaction and a more active role of the author in the publishing process.

Other examples

There are several other examples within scholarly publishing, which offer a more interactive and collaborative peer review. The Journal of Experimental Medicine (JExpMed) employs the process of Reviewer collaboration, which provides an opportunity for reviewers to read each other's report before sending their recommendations to the author. The primary purpose of this new process is to improve the quality and effectiveness of peer review. The journal Science has a process very similar to JExpMed's, which they call cross-review. After all reviews are submitted, reviewers are invited to read the other reviews and have the option to make additional comments

⁸ <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/pages/authors/>
<https://disqus.com/profile/login/?next=https%3A//bmjwebdevblog.disqus.com/>

⁹ https://bmjopen.bmj.com/pages/authors/#peer_review_process

within a limited time frame¹⁰. However, transparency of the process is not advanced by the fact that this review is conducted anonymously. The review itself is shared only with the author, and possibly with other reviewers, but not the identity of the reviewers.

Summary

The examples of alternative review processes discussed above reflect the researchers' attitudes toward the different open peer review attributes we learnt from the user centered survey results. There is a demand for more transparency in the review process, but this openness is mainly welcomed in connection to open reports, and in a majority of the cases, in connection to open interactions among editors, authors and reviewers. Although some of these alternative solutions do not embrace the full transparency by publishing identities and allowing wider peer participation in the review process, they are excellent initiatives contributing to a wider uptake of a more open evaluation system.

3.1.2 Preprint dissemination

As traditional publishing and its peer review methods proves to be a lengthy process, preprints offer speedier dissemination accelerating scientific progress. It carries several benefits for scholarly communication being more fair, open, and transparent with peers and the public (Enago publishing, 2018). Despite the fact that preprint content enables fruitful discussion and feedback from volunteer peer reviewers and commenters, it is criticized as a publishing methodology due to the lack of organized peer review connected to it (Amaral, 2018). The quality control mechanisms added to preprints could also help to identify and filter out low quality.

Preprint servers

Alternative methods of dissemination include the publishing of preprints, mainly through disciplinary repositories and preprint servers. Preprints are widely used in the physical sciences and now emerging in the life sciences and other fields. The widely held pioneering and most-successful example is arXiv, which covers preprints in the field of physics, mathematics and further quantitative disciplines (launched in August 1991). Further preprint archives launched during the 1990s include the Social Science Research Network (SSRN, 1994) and Research Papers in Economics (RePEc, 1997), which is based on a network of databases. Several other fields followed these examples only years later. bioRxiv, a preprint server provided by Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory for the life sciences, launched in 2013, was soon followed by SocArxiv (2016) in the social sciences, engrXiv (2016) for engineering, AgriXiv (2017) in agriculture and allied sciences, and several other recent additions, e.g. paleorxiv (2017), MarXiv (2017), and the French server for preprints in all the scientific fields Frenxiv (2018). Many of these are hosted by the Center for Open Science (COS)¹¹. Several publishers also host preprints (e.g. PeerJ Preprints, the MDPI's platform Preprints, and ChemRxiv operated by the American Chemical Society).

The emergence of preprint servers indicates a trend and a need for early communication and registration of research findings, and transparency into the research process (Görögh, 2018).

¹⁰ <http://www.sciencemag.org/authors/peer-review-science-publications>

¹¹ Collection of OSF preprints: <https://osf.io/preprints>

Figure 6. Preprint growth by month. Source: PrePubMed. Monthly statistics for April 2018. http://www.prepubmed.org/monthly_stats/

These platforms typically run internal checks to ensure that the posted work is of scientific nature. Social platforms such as ResearchGate or Academia are also used for preprint posting, but they are different in terms of their purpose. Publishers are more and more establishing new methods to link preprints and the final journal version of the record to make scientific discovery more open.

Among the advantages of disseminating research results via preprints, we can include immediate dissemination, wider recognition of achievements in grant proposals, shifting copyright ownership to authors, increase discoverability of related outputs through DOI. The practical challenges of preprint dissemination are related to a variety of issues including technical and social aspects of publishing. Researchers carry fears of having their ideas scooped, which indicates that sharing involves taking risks and feeling vulnerable of plagiarism. The technical challenges also include version consolidation and increasing the discoverability of preprints in different disciplinary communities.

There is a common concern that preprints may be less reliable than peer-reviewed articles. Papers from preprint repositories are cited and used in research, but still they have the disadvantage of lacking a peer review evaluation attached to them (Adam, 2010). There are several initiatives, which attempt to overcome this problem by introducing peer review solutions to preprint depositing.

ASAPbio (asapbio.org) recommends a scientist-driven, journal-agnostic peer review service that produces an Evaluated Preprint and facilitates subsequent publication in a journal. After submitting the work to a preprint server or *Peer Feedback*, researchers request evaluation. The authors suggest a list of possible referees and *Peer Feedback* will select and contact referees. It is a fee-based service, so authors are charged a fee from which reviewers are compensated for their work. The Evaluated Preprint can be included in grants, job applications, and promotions, and can also be submitted to journal publication. Articles going through *Peer Feedback* are envisioned to go through another review only for journal suitability. This system promotes better journal matching with less rejection since editors will have better information on the submission (Vale, 2018).

Figure 7. Peer Feedback. Source: Vale, R., Hyman, T. and Polka J. (2018). Peer Feedback. ASAPbio.

Due to disciplinary differences and various journal policies, posting the preprint version of a manuscript and then submitting it to scientific journals for publishing are not always compatible processes. But, ASAPbio provides an excellent example how preprint depositing complements journal publishing in the field of biology.

At the ASAPbio meeting in February 2016, different stakeholders (academics, publishers, funders) shared and negotiated their perspectives on preprint dissemination and their role in the scholarly publishing system. The meeting goals were to analyze the roles that preprints might play in communicating results in biology and to debate the potential advantages and disadvantages of greater use of preprints for the progress of science, career development, and the integrity of the scientific record (Berg, 2016). All participating stakeholders agreed on several key issues, which could contribute to redefining the positions of preprint in publishing:

- Posting on a recognized preprint server does not constitute prior publication or a breach of embargo policies,
- comments on the preprint would help to make the subsequent formal review process more efficient and could result in an improved final manuscript
- time-stamped preprints help attributing scientific findings to researchers, and establishing priority also will depend on credibility gained through peer review.

Overlay journals

Another option to provide peer review for preprints is through overlay journals. The main advantage of this type of journal, besides adding peer review as an additional layer on top of collections of preprints, that it uses the pre-existing infrastructure and content of preprint servers. The reason they are termed “overlay” journals is that the articles remain on the preprint server in their peer reviewed state, with the “journals” mostly comprising a simple list of links to these versions (Tennant, 2017).

Another definition explains the overlay journal as a journal that does not publish any original articles but rather selects articles that exist elsewhere, adds certain value to the selection, and publishes the results as a service to its user base (Van den Sompel, 2016). The overlay aspect of this type of dissemination refers to its structure: the way it relates to other services. The overlay journal also offers an additional layer of quality assurance either

through relevance or significance¹². One of the great examples of an overlay journal is provided by Discrete Analysis, which is an online journal with links to mathematics papers hosted on the preprint server arXiv. Researchers submit their papers directly from arXiv to the journal, which evaluates them by conventional peer review (Ball, 2016).

Although this publishing form is mostly discussed in relation to preprint servers, it can also be connected to repository content. The overlay concept enhances repositories by increasing their usefulness to researchers and improving their sustainability with value-added services. Overlay journals provide an opportunity for institutions to engage directly with specific subjects and disciplines using the institutional repositories to develop and populate journals.

Quality assessment can be added to this form of publishing as overlay peer-review functionalities. For example, the Open Peer Review Module for repositories, developed by Open Scholar in association with OpenAIRE, is an open source software plug-in which adds overlay peer review functionalities to repositories using the DSpace software (Ross-Hellauer, 2017). Another option for peer review is provided by Open Scholar in the form of author-guided open peer review.¹³ This research assessment process complementary to journal-handled peer review where authors themselves can invite experts to openly evaluate their work. Reviews are subject to commentary and evaluation by the entire community. Author-guided OPR offers a flexible system of evaluation since it can be implemented at any stage of an article's lifetime.

Open platforms

The European Commission plans to launch an open access publishing platform (Open Research Europe) which will also host preprints as an add-on feature. It was founded as a reaction to the European Commission's call for tender to build an "Open Research Europe Publication Platform." Some scepticism was expressed among researchers about this initiative. The publishing platform will be available to the beneficiaries of all scientific projects financed by the European Commission, and will provide an open access publishing venue managing the entire publication process with an open peer review system. The question arises how its use can be incentivized among researchers. Lack of integration and seamless transition between multiple platforms may lead to the loss of focus and to fragmentation.

As an alternative approach the TTOA has proposed the development of the "Open Publication Platform (OPP)", which consists of two pillars: (1) a submission portal that serves as a preprint publication channel and channels articles to the journals preferred by the authors. Peer-review reports are portable and are carried along with the paper from one journal to the next, with authors revising their paper as a function of the reviews, and (2) a modern platform hosting the journals' peer-reviewed and published articles. All publishers in the TTOA Consortium have agreed that the publication fee will not exceed €1400 per article on average (TTOA, 2018).

¹² <http://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/19081/1/19081.pdf>

¹³ <http://www.openscholar.org.uk/open-peer-review/>

Figure 8. Peer review connected to preprint dissemination. Source: <https://www.fairopenaccess.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Public-statement-TTOA-consortium-30may18-def.pdf>

Summary

There are continuous developments in the preprint publishing scene with new discipline specific preprint services being launched (INA-Axiv, LISSA, MindRxiv, paleorXiv, NutriXiv, and SportRxiv), or new overlay journals being announced (biOverlay), or new tools being created to make the preprint discovery more user friendly (new service allowing users to read arXiv articles in HTML instead of the traditional PDF format) (Tennant, 2018). In order to realize the full potential of preprint publishing in the future, several issues should be addressed. Preprint would be valued more if linking between preprints and peer reviewed publications was a common feature. We need clear guidelines and policies on the use of preprints, and standards and licenses for processes on submitting, sharing and re-using preprint materials (e.g. COPE¹⁴). Furthermore, educating researchers with regard to the licenses and publishers’ policies on preprint dissemination could clear the confusion about this form of publishing.

3.1.3 Decoupled review

Independent peer review services are often included in the discourse on the transforming scholarly publishing scene. Decoupled peer review, as defined in D3.1, offers a change to the scholarly communication process by separating the review process from the journals and publishers and offering it as an independent service to authors.

The decoupled model of peer review entails initiatives such as the *Peerage of Science* (peerageofscience.org), *RUBRIQ* (rubriq.com), and *Axios Review* (axiosreview.org; closed in 2017) which operate peer review services separately from any publishing venue. These services offer users the traditional methods of peer review (single or double blind) with a workflow very similar to established journal-based review process. After the author’s submission of the manuscript to the provided platforms, the service

¹⁴ <https://publicationethics.org/about>

manages referee invitations and rounds of revisions, after which the manuscript and the referee reports are forwarded to a journal of the author's choice. These services are linked to numerous journals which agree to accept the reviews issued by the platforms, and submission to publish the manuscript can be referred from one journal to another within the participating journal pool. These platforms operate fee-based services which usually covers the remuneration of the invited referees (Tennant, 2017).

The sustainability of these services and their uptake among authors and publishers raise several questions in respect of all involved stakeholders. The basis of this system is the existence of a critical mass of researchers with sufficient financial resources (the review rates can reach as high as \$600). Research communities should provide sufficient numbers of authors paying for the services and reviewers. On the other hand, publishers have to trust external peer review systems and their choices of suitable reviewers. The anonym review reports should score high on quality and reliability in order to be accepted by publishers on face value. The number of participating scholarly journals should also need to be high. If the participation in this system does not seem rewarding for researchers due to the reduced number of journals affiliated with the system, the success of the model will be compromised. Finally, reviewers must receive adequate incentives to participate. The motivation can be of financial or academic nature. In the case of Rubriq, reviewers obtain an economic compensation for each report performed. While Peerage of Science offers publication of review reports as citable publishing in Proceedings of Peerage of Science or in other journals (Fresco-Santalla, 2014).

Another example of independent peer review methodology is offered by Open Scholar, which launched a project with an innovative, journal-independent peer review approach. The Self-Journal of Science (SJS) is an open access repository that provides free peer review service with community involvement. On the one hand, SJS is a platform where scholars can freely curate published scientific articles from any source into their self-journal. On the other hand, authors can also freely upload their articles on SJS, where added open peer review features will allow to assess them.¹⁵

However, the commercial future of decoupled peer review does not look promising. The closing of Axios Reviews, according to Tim Vines, founder and chief operating officer, was due to several reasons: price sensitivity, entrenched workflows, and the culture of conducting in-house peer review (Davis, 2017). The sustainability of Peerage of Science also depends on incoming investments. Peerage is functioning at the moment because the costs are kept low. However, to hire a team and accelerate submission rate will need serious investors who accept current operational terms – states Janne Seppänen, Co-Founder, and Managing Director of Peerage (Davis, 2017).

The standalone review systems operate similarly to the cascading and portable peer review models. Authors are allowed to take the review reports as they look for a suitable journal for their manuscript without having to repeat the whole reviewing process. The primary aim of these models to reduce the amount of work being done in academic publishing and speed up the dissemination process. It offers a good solution to avoid the same papers from being reviewed over and over again, saving authors, editors, and referees valuable time and making the publication system more effective.

Portable review is normally a feature of mega journals taking place only within a publisher, but some organizations are also building teams to share reviews more broadly. In 2013, eLife, BioMed Central (BMC), the Public Library of Science (PLoS), and the European Molecular Biology Organization (EMBO) formed a peer review consortium, which operates by the principles of portable review. Authors, submitting their manuscripts to a participating journal in the consortium, and are not accepted by that journal, are able to resubmit their paper,

¹⁵ <http://sjscience.org/>

with the review reports, to any other journal in the consortium. Reviewers can opt out of having their reports forwarded, or of having their identity disclosed (Clarke, 2013).

Independent reviewers are also employed within grant application processes. Invited experts provide funding agency decision makers with independent perspectives and judgments. These qualitative evaluations provide program managers and procurement specialists with comparative information from contrasting perspectives that they can use in judging which work has the greatest likelihood of meeting the goals of their program¹⁶. Review by independent experts is also used to evaluate interim progress or project results and conclusions to help guide program decisions how to continue the program or to make corrections in approach. Reviewers here are also compensated for their work.

3.2 Peer review in various settings

Research on open peer review within the framework of the OpenUP project also entails the examination of peer review alternatives in different settings. These micro studies basically offer validation to the open peer review system described in the landscape scan (D3.1) and explore the way a more open and transparent review methodology can be connected to various research product outputs and practices. In the following section some of these pilot studies conducted within the context of various work package tasks, are described: (1) reviewing the research flow (T3.2)¹⁷, (2) peer review for research data (WP6 Pilot 2)¹⁸ and (3) peer review at conferences (WP6 Pilot 1).¹⁹

3.2.1 Reviewing the research flow

Science's digital shift and impact on Open Science

An increasing number of researchers conduct their research adopting ICT tools for the production and processing of research products. In the last decade, research infrastructures (organizational and technological facilities supporting research activities) are investing in “e-infrastructures” that leverage ICT tools, services, guidelines and policies to support the digital practices of their community of researchers. To find an analogy with traditional science, e-infrastructures are the place where researchers can grow and define the boundaries of their *digital laboratories*, i.e. the subset of assets they use to run an experiment. Researchers run their digital *experiments* (e.g. simulations, data analysis) taking advantage of the digital laboratory assets and generate new *research data* and *computational products* (e.g. software, R algorithms, computational workflows) that can be shared with other researchers of the same community, to be discovered, accessed and reused.

The role of digital laboratories is therefore twofold: on the one hand they support researchers in their advancement of science, offering the facilities needed for their daily activities; on the other hand, they foster the dissemination of research within the research community, supporting discovery, access to, sharing, and reuse of digital research products. In fact, their digital nature offers unprecedented opportunities for scientists, who can share not only scientific literature describing their findings, but also the digital results that they managed to produce, together with the digital laboratory itself. Those features are fundamental for an effective implementation of the Open Science (OS) paradigm (European Commission, 2015, 2016). OS can also be defined as a set of practices of science, advocated by all scientific/scholarly communication stakeholders (i.e., research funders, research and academic organizations, and researchers), according to which the research activities and all the products they

¹⁶ <https://www.orau.org/documents/about/ORAU%20Peer%20Review%20White%20Paper.pdf>

¹⁷ Bardi, A. (2017).

¹⁸ Luzi, D. and Ruggieri, R. (2018).

¹⁹ Zendel, O. (2018)

generate should be freely available, under terms that enable their findability, accessibility, re-use, and re-distribution²⁰. The effects of Open Science are mainly the following:

- Reproduce research activities: let other users reproduce the experiments of a research activity;
- Transparently assess research activities: evaluate findings based on the ability to repeat science, but also on the quality of the individual products of science, i.e. literature, research data, computational products and experiments.

If supported with adequate degrees of openness, scientists may find the conditions to *repeat* (“same research activity, same laboratory”), *replicate* (“same research activity, different laboratory”), *reproduce* (“same research activity, different input parameters”), or *re-use* (“using the product of a research activity into another research activity”) the research activities, thereby maximizing transparency and exploitation of scientific findings (De Roure, 2009).

Defining the research flow in the digital era

A *research activity* is carried on as a sequence of actions constituting the *research flow*. The research flow is made of a number of *experiments*, realized as sequence of steps in the context of a *digital laboratory*, executed by scientists driven by the ultimate intent of proving an initial scientific thesis. In the following we shall refer to:

- An *experiment* is defined in the following as a goal-driven sequence of steps set to verify a thesis, and whose result may inspire further experiments to address the target of the overarching research activity.
- A *digital laboratory* can be defined as a pool of digital assets (e.g. on-line tools, desktop tools, methodologies, standards) used by scientists to perform the steps of an experiment and generate research products.
- A *research product* is defined here as any digital object generated during the research flow that was relevant to complete the research activity and (possibly) relevant for its interpretation once the research activity has been completed. Products are digital objects, whose human consumption depends on computer programs; they are concrete items that can be discovered, accessed, and possibly re-used under given access rights. Examples are datasets in a data repository (e.g. sea observations in the PANGAEA repository), but also entries in domain databases (e.g. proteins in UNIPROT), software (e.g. models implemented as R algorithms in GitHub), and of course the scientific article, reporting about the findings of a research activity.

A research activity may therefore generate a number of research products, which represent the digital tangible results of the research activity and enable scientists to draw their conclusions. Indeed, several “intermediate” products are generated on the way to the end, e.g. input and outputs of unsuccessful experiments, versions of the final products to be refined. A research activity can therefore be described by a *research flow*, pictured in Figure 9, as a sequence of steps $S_1 \dots S_n$, potentially grouped into *experiments*, carried out in the frame of a digital laboratory. More specifically, each step S_i of a research flow is in turn a sequence of actions enacted by humans, possibly by means of digital laboratory assets, that may require or produce (intermediate) research products. Clearly, some (or all) of the research products generated during the research flow may become, at some point in time, new assets of a digital laboratory. According to this scenario, in the simplest case of theoretical sciences, the research flow might be constituted by one experiment consisting of one step of “formulation of hypothesis” and one step of “thinking”, whose final product is a scientific article. In a slightly more complex scenario, a research flow may be composed by one experiment, whose steps include data collection, data processing, and result analysis, with a final last step producing the article and the research data output to be published.

²⁰ <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/foster-taxonomy/open-science-definition>

Figure 9. The research flow. Source: Bardi A., Casarosa V., Manghi P., (2017). OpenUP Deliverable D3.2 A specification of the scientific method and scientific communication. <https://osf.io/hvydq/wiki/D3.2/>

Peer-reviewing the research flow

As stated before, in the digital science era, the ability to share research products, in combination with digital laboratories, opens the way to Open Science principles. According to these principles, science should be open not only once that it is concluded, but also while it is being performed. In other words, scientists should, as much as possible, make their methodologies, thinking and findings available to enable/maximize collaboration and reuse by the community. The digital laboratory becomes therefore the core of this vision as it is the place providing the assets needed by the researchers to carry on their research flow and at the same time the place that provides the generated research products, for sharing and peer-reviewing. For example, scientists performing analysis of data using R scripts, may use a digital laboratory equipped with the software RStudio offered as-a-service by an online provider (e.g. BlueBridge e-infrastructure powered by D4Science) and a repository where they can store/share their R scripts and their input and output datasets (e.g. Zenodo.org).

Depending on the technological advances developed and adopted by the research community in the digital laboratory, scientists may generate products whose goal is not just sharing “findings” but also sharing “methodologies”. Methodology products are digital objects encoding experiments or the research flow itself. As such they are generated to describe/model the actions performed by the scientists and, in principle, could enable a machine-assisted repetition of those actions. The availability of research products at various stages of the research flow makes it possible to introduce peer review stages during the on-going research activity. Specifically, depending on the kind of products made available, different degrees of peer review may be attained, to support manual but also machine-supported reproducibility and consequently enforce more transparent and objective research flow peer review practices.

In case of manual reproducibility, the reviewers are provided with a description of the research flow in the form of an article, together with references to the digital laboratory assets and research products (datasets, software, computational products) produced during the research flow. Referred research products are those that are considered relevant by the article's authors, often a subset of the products generated by the research flow. Reproducibility and research flow assessment strongly depends on humans, both in the way the research flow is described and in the ability of the reviewers, and in general of other researchers, to repeat the same actions.

In case of machine reproducibility of experiments, the reviewers are provided with an experiment, inclusive of generated products and the digital assets from the digital laboratory needed to perform the experiment. Such research products factor out from the scientific article the concept of experiment and research flow, making it a tangible, machine-processable and shareable result of science (Bechhofer, 2013). Reproducibility can be objectively supported by a machine and finally evaluated, but the assessment of methodology as a whole still depends on humans. In fact, sharing inputs, outputs and processes is often not enough for a human to understand the experiment and its value. Information about the investigation in which the experiment is conducted is necessary in order to add context to the experiment and to make the interpretation easier.

In case of machine reproducibility of research flows the reviewers are provided with technology to reproduce experiments and research flows. In this scenario, human judgment is supported by machines, which can provide a higher degree of transparency. Relevant examples for this scenario are protocols.io, ArrayExpress and FAIRDOMHub. The guidelines that they adopt (MIAME²¹, MINSEQE²² and the ISA framework (Sansone, 2012)) encourage researchers at providing a complete, structured description of the whole research flow. However, they fail at fully supporting research flow peer review for the following reasons:

- They model an individual experiment rather than an arbitrary sequence of them;
- They generally do not model the scientific method, but focus on the actual sequences of steps forming an experiment;
- They focus on repeatability/reproducibility of an experiment rather than peer reviewing of all products and of the research flow (research methodology).
- They do not make a distinction between successful and not successful experiments.

²¹ MIAMI guidelines (Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment): <http://fged.org/projects/miame/>

²² MINSEQE guidelines (Minimum Information about a high-throughput SEQuencing Experiment): <http://fged.org/projects/minseqe/>

Figure 10. Entities of research flow. Source: Bardi A., Casarosa V., Manghi P., (2017). OpenUP Deliverable D3.2 A specification of the scientific method and scientific communication. <https://osf.io/hvydq/wiki/D3.2/>

In Fig. 10 we represent the main relationships between all the different entities involved in the machine-assisted peer review of the research flow. Of course “Experiments” and “Research Flow” are intended as the digital objects representing them. For more details on the state of the art on current trends for the peer review of the research flows, please refer to Deliverable D3.2 (Bardi, 2017).

Remarks and challenges

Peer reviewing the whole research flow is certainly the most complete conception of evaluation and assessment of science. Its modeling includes the scientific method, which corresponds to how science is performed (the structuring of scientific thinking), and the experiments, which correspond to model how science was actually carried out in terms of steps, digital laboratory assets, and generated research products. Existing approaches nicely solve some of these issues, but none of them tackles the complete problem. Existing solutions have reproducibility of science as their main objective, rather than research flow peer review, hence they focus on the executable representation of digital objects encoding successful experiments. Such objects express the logic of an experiment but do not describe the overall research flow of which they are a final step; not only, such objects do not describe the scientific method underlying the research flow. For example if a scientist adopts a research flow devised as a cycle of experiments, refining their inputs and outputs until a certain success threshold is reached, using the approaches described above the scientist will publish only the last execution of the experiment, together with the research products required to reproduce it. Overall, these observations lead to the following considerations.

Ongoing research flow peer review. In contrast with traditional peer review models, which assess scientific results only once the research activity has been successful, peer review could/should also be applied during the ongoing research flow, as a sort of monitoring and interim evaluation process. Ongoing research flow peer review would also increase the possibility for a researcher to demonstrate the validity and trustworthiness of the research being carried out and its (intermediate) results.

Negative results. By sharing intermediate research flow experiments and steps a researcher would also open up the publishing of negative results, that contradict the establish way of thinking (Weintraub, 2016). This practice could have a twofold positive effect: on the one hand, the researcher might receive comments and advice from colleagues, on the other hand, he/she would help the community by suggesting avoiding the same “mistakes” (Di Leo, 2017).

Machine assisted vs human assisted review. Today, there is no formal (and technologically supported) distinction between the steps of an experiment (and of the research flow) that should be peer-reviewed by humans (e.g. novelty and impact of a research flow and its final products) and those that could be reviewed by machines (e.g. conformance to given structural and semantic requirements of data and software (Shanahan, 2016)). It would be desirable to have tools for “machine-assisted peer-review”, based on the very same digital laboratory assets that generated the research products, e.g. verify the research product conformance to the requirements and standards of a given domain. Although humans would still play a central role in the peer-review process, such tools would support reviewers facing challenges going beyond their capabilities (e.g. checking the quality of each record in a database).

Scientific method review. In order to achieve an omni-comprehensive review of the research flow, reviewers would benefit from viewing a description of the underlying scientific process. This approach is the one underlying the Registered Reports proposed by the Centre of Open Science²³ which however is concerned with human peer review of literature products. None of the existing approaches aims at a peer review approach driven by a digital representation of the scientific process (a specific type of methodology product) where the representation of a given research flow is intended as a peer reviewable instance of such process.

Towards research flow peer review

The implementation of a fully-fledged research flow peer review methodology has requirements (tools and practices) that differ from those identified in Open Science for reproducibility. Reproducibility of science and its underlying principles are indeed crucial to support transparent peer review, but existing practices are not enough to fully address research flow peer review. In order to support this kind of peer review, reviewers should evaluate science by means of a user-friendly environment that transparently relies on the underlying digital laboratory assets, hides their ICT complexity, and gives guarantees of repeatability and reproducibility recognized by the community.

In this section we sketch some ideas in the direction of the definition of a framework for the representation of a research flow peer review for a given discipline of science. Such a framework might become the scaffolding on top of which tools for supporting the ongoing peer review of research flows might be developed by “real-time hooking” to the underlying digital laboratory where scientists are carrying out their research flow. Such tools would abstract over the complexity of the research activity and offer user-friendly dashboards to examine the scientific process adopted, explore the ongoing research flow, and evaluate its intermediate experiments and relative products. In a less advanced implementation, such tools might provide scientific process and research flow to reviewers once the research activity has been terminated, inclusive of all intermediate experiments, steps and research products.

To this aim, the framework should be built around the notion of *research flow review templates*. These are representations of the scientific processes in terms of patterns (sequences and cycles) of experiments and relative steps to be peer reviewed; note that such templates should include all and only experiments, steps, and relative “signatures” for which peer-review is required and supported. In other words a research flow template is not intended to describe the detailed experiments and steps of a research activity but to model which subset of these is relevant to assess the quality of the research flow.

For example, consider the scientific process in Figure 11, which models one experiment repeatedly executed until the research activity is successful. At every iteration, the experiment designs (1) and instruments the digital laboratory with processing algorithms (2), collects input data (3), performs the analysis (4) to produce output data and finally it publishes (5) all such products. Then we may assume that the only review checkpoint is the one of

²³ <https://cos.io/rr/>

“publication” (5), where input data and digital laboratory assets are made available. The corresponding research template would model the very same cycle and be made of one experiment including a single step of peer review, the one of publication mentioned above. Ongoing peer review tools would allow reviewers to select a given execution of the experiment in time, explore and assess input and output data, and re-execute the given step given the relative products. Of course, such tools should be equipped with functionalities to provide feedback and evaluation.

Figure 11. Research lifecycle adopted from the research process model by Kraker & Lindstaedt. Source: OpenUP WP4 team, D4.1.

Several sciences are making use of shared scientific process patterns, for example in clinical trials²⁴, where sample-based experiments are structured and documented according to established protocols in order for other scientists to transparently understand the thinking underlying given findings. In order for a community to provide a specification of the peer-reviewable part of its research flow and therefore build adequate tools in support of reviewers, a simple formal framework capable of describing the structure of a given community research flow review template(s) should be available. Each template should reflect one particular way of performing science, capturing the steps which should be subject to peer review (each community may define more than one template). At the same time, templates enforce researchers at complying with certain expectations when producing science. Templates express common behaviour, encode good practices, enable reproducibility and transparent evaluation of science. To make an analogy, the structure of a template should reflect the structure of a recipe for cooking. It should specify a list of all the (types of) products needed from the digital laboratory at each step of the research flow (the ingredients) and should mandate a detailed description (machine actionable) of all the steps to be executed (the mixing and the cooking) in order to reproduce the research results (the cake).

Such research flow review framework should encompass the following concepts (see figure 12):

- *Research flow template*: the model of research flow to be followed by scientists in terms of experiments, including cycles, conditions, etc. to be peer reviewed;
- *Step and experiment signatures*, intended as:
 - *Result products*: the classes of products required and returned by such steps (datasets, literature, computational products);
 - *Assets of the digital laboratory* (which are not necessarily a research product) required for the execution of the step or of the experiment.
 - *Methodology products*: the classes of digital objects encoding experiments;

²⁴ Clinical Trial Protocol Development, <http://hub.ucsf.edu/protocol-development> (last accessed 31st of May 2017)

- *Different classes of literature*: ranging from documentation to descriptions of scientific methods.

Sharing a framework of this kind allows the realization of *research publishing tools* and *review tools* that allow scientists to produce products as expected and other scientists to access such products, for reuse, reproducibility, and review. As mentioned above, to be effective and used in practice, such tools should be:

- *Integrated with digital laboratory assets used to perform science*: scientists should focus on developing their science rather than publishing it; the process of creating research products and methodology products should be delegated as much as possible to machines, together with tracking the history of the actual research flow; digital laboratory assets require research publishing tools (e.g. wrappers, mediators) capable of flanking the experiment functionality they support with functionality for packaging and publishing the relative products, so that review tools can benefit from those;
- *Easy to use*: user-friendly enough for scientists to access machine-assisted review tools without development skills; reviewers should be able to view the actual research flow, to view its current stage of development, and to apply machine-assisted validation from end-user interfaces;
- *Trustworthy*: easy to use is a property that should come with guarantees of fairness, typically endorsed by the community adopting research publishing and review tools.

Implementing this vision raises serious challenges as it requires not only endorsement of the research communities but also cultural convergence (i.e. rigorous behaviour in performing science). Most importantly, the realization and maintenance of tools for publishing and review whose cost do not easily find a donor in communities that are typically formed by scientists rather than institutions.

Figure 12. Research flow templates concepts. Source: Bardi A., Casarosa V., Manghi P., (2017). OpenUP Deliverable D3.2 A specification of the scientific method and scientific communication. <https://osf.io/hvydq/wiki/D3.2/>

Use case scenario

The research flow review framework supports the definition of research flow templates to model common discipline-specific patterns (best practices for a given discipline). Task 3.5 is currently developing experimental templates for two specific use cases. The first one is in geothermal energy science, which is studying the energy generated and stored in the Earth. Geothermal research includes on-site activities for subsoil data measurements

(in some cases already collected data is re-used) and digital activities for data curation and analysis. Typical research activities in this field are chemical analysis of rock samples and the geologic and electromagnetic modelling of the subsoil with a technique called “forward modelling”. The second use case is in Archeology, i.e. the study of ancient cultures and civilizations through examination of the artifacts (objects and or buildings) found over or (more often) under the ground. A typical research flow in archeology is comprised of many different steps, going from preliminary studies to identify a place of interest to the final excavation report.

Summary

The implementation of the research flow review templates contributes to open peer review practices on two levels: on the one hand it reinforces reproducibility of science and its underlying principles, and on the other hand they offer a transparent tool to evaluate scientific processes.

3.2.2 Peer review for research data

Open peer review for research data in Social science

Similarly to peer review of publications, data peer review is the process of the quality assessment of a dataset performed by experts in the same field. However, data quality assessment is a complex process that has to consider the different phases of the data lifecycle, starting from the development of a data management plan (DMP) at the initial stage of a scientific project to the publication of its results. Data publication (some authors speaks about Publication with capital letter, Lawrence et al. 2011, Mayernik et al. 2015) that undergoes a peer review process validating data quality is currently performed in data journals and data repositories. However, analyses by Candela et al. (2015), Carpenter (2017) show that there is room for improvement, as peer review in data journals varies a lot and is mostly focused on metadata, rather than data themselves, aiming to assess the documentation and metadata description that facilitate data reuse. Assante et al. (2016), in the analysis of generalist repositories (Zenodo, Dryad, Figshare etc.), also come to the conclusion that different criteria and quality control mechanisms are implemented based on varied policies and/or guidelines. Best practices of data validation can be taken from the publication in trusted data repositories (Callaghan et al. 2014), in which the data quality control can be considered a form of review by experts in the field carried out in a pre-publication phase. Moreover, the possibility to post their comments and evaluations by end users may be considered as a trait of open participation in OPR performed in a post-publication phase. Other important indicators of impacts can be developed using data citation counts and/or statics of use, which are considered crucial aspects to improve data sharing.

In social sciences data peer review is at its initial stage in fact there is only one data journal covering Humanities and Social sciences: “Research Data Journal (RDJ)”. Considering trusted data repositories best practices are generally related to national repositories (i.e. UK Data Archive, GESIS and DANS) and international initiatives CESSDA at a European level and ICPSR. Based on the landscape analysis performed (D6.2) we selected, among the different communities contacted, the Human Mortality Database (HMD). As predefined in the methodology, interviews with the HMD top managers were conducted in January 2018 as well as a user survey developed in collaboration with HMD was sent out at end of March 2018.

From the interviews some best practices emerged that can drive the adoption of data quality assessment, and hence peer review, as well as some principles that can incentivize other scientific communities to share their research data. As stated by the HMD interviewees, the guiding principles to create an open access database were: comparability, flexibility, accessibility and reproducibility. Comparability was reached using a uniform, scientific methodology to calculate the various statistics of the 39 countries included in the database. Flexibility was achieved in the analysis of results using a uniform set of procedures for each population, but at the same time giving significant attention to each population in terms of its history and socio-political development. This is

achieved thanks to the experiences and knowledge of country specialists, who are persons in charge of collecting data from a specific number of countries, interact with statistical offices, check data consistency and provide population statistics together with a country report that explains specificity and motivation of analysis. Accessibility was guaranteed from the beginning by free of charge access of data, as well as by the provision of data in an open, no-proprietary format. Reproducibility is provided by the reconstruction of the data lifecycle that includes the availability of raw data, the method applied, the related results as well as the explanatory documentation. The best practice is a transparent way of data managing and sharing that has two central phases of data validation. The first one is carried out by the country specialists, who analyze the raw data according to a common predefined checklist that verifies consistency and plausibility of data. The second one is carried out in a collaborative way within the HMD team that validate the statistics before their publication, each time the database is updated.

Moreover, a successful component of the HMD was its collaborative approach that is based on a strong scientific interest in the field as well as on the trust among the involved community that only recently has formally signed a Memorandum of understanding.

The interviews also highlighted some indications that confirm some concerns already mentioned by other surveys. Interviewees stressed the importance of having a strong commitment of the organization in supporting the development of data infrastructures. This pertains different aspects: a long-term financial support (beyond the project duration), a policy endorsement on open data as well as a formal recognition of scientists for the efforts in data curation and quality assurance.

Results of the user survey are currently under evaluation. However, some preliminary results can be reported. When asked to indicate the advantages in using HMD, respondents reported most often the following options: the easily accessible data, the comparability over time and across-countries, and the long time periods of the data available. Moreover, looking at the final overall comments provided by some respondents, important indications on users' needs and expectations can be drawn. Among the suggestions of improvements, there is the request of expanding the number of countries to be included in the HMD, as well as the availability of tools that facilitate data download, such as machine-readable formats or the possibility to host HMD and/or user-contributed code to facilitate the analysis and thus the re-use. Among the many appreciations reported by respondents, some of them summarize well the characteristics of the HMD that could be applied to increase data publication and quality assessment in other Social Sciences contexts. This pertains the availability of the source data and the trustworthiness of the database (“It is also easy to use and reference, and a trustworthy source, so I don’t have the need to look elsewhere for data”) or as a respondent reported: “You are the gold standard in the field and an example of the good work that can be done, but we need more like you to have the rest of the world a la HMD”.

3.2.3 Review at conferences

The review process at conferences shares many aspects with peer reviewing for journals. However, given the much shorter timeframes (time between submission and publication at traditional journals can often reach over two years) and the typically higher number submissions, the peer review process at conferences has to be efficient and fast. Here, many OPR aspects can help conference organizers to cope with scaling issues and tight deadlines.

Figure 13. Comparison of traditional peer review vs. OPR at conferences. Source:

The OpenUP Pilot 1: “Open Peer Review for Conferences” evaluated multiple OPR techniques at two different conference venues. The community (authors and reviews) as well as the conference organizers perceived the approach in general as very positive (see D6.3 for details). These specific techniques were tested and proved to be useful during the pilot:

- Start with a traditional (“double-blind”) review round. During the following rebuttal phase, the authors may choose to withdraw their submission from the conference/competition. If they submit an answer to the reviewers questions and stay in the process, then this submission can move into an “Open Identify”/“Open Report” phase: the submission, the review, the author’s names and the reviewer’s names are visible within the submission system. This allows all conference attendees to see accepted and rejected papers.
- All participants (authors submitting a paper to the conference) are automatically assigned as reviewers during the review phase. Asking for two “lay-man’s” reviews seems to be an acceptable effort for authors and adds additional feedback for quality assurance purposes and content improvement.
- When stakes are not high (informative/networking conference), then comments with a length of about one paragraph are enough to communicate personal preferences and potential improvements. More text and stricter template-style reviews can create better quality reviews but also require a lot more time from both reviewers and authors alike.
- Public decision/voting process in an “Open Report” scenario can help conference organizers to steer the conference content towards their audience. Here, all conference attendees can participate and vote on the submitted articles. This approach is only viable with a limited number of contributions (e.g. below 20) so that it is feasible that each attendee has a chance of reading all articles beforehand.

4. Missing elements

The thorough analysis of the peer review methods and processes resulted in both (1) the examination of available peer review alternatives, and (2) the identification of missing elements of the transforming peer review system. The following section examines these missing elements (evidence-based research on open peer review, incentives to participate in the review process, and training reviewers) and provides recommendation on how they can be built into scholarly communication process in order to ensure a wider uptake of open peer review tools and services. The section includes the description of our research and efforts to develop a framework to foster more evidence-based studies on the efficacy of open peer review (OPR)²⁵, as well as to develop a model framework for the implementation of OPR.²⁶ It also describes the training activities which help to increase awareness on open peer review tools and to motivate researchers to get involved in open peer review.

4.1 Evidence based research on the efficacy of OPR

A part of WP3 activities was dedicated to creating a framework for data-sharing amongst publishers regarding OPR and construct a shared agenda for assessment of the efficacy of OPR approaches. The findings were gathered iteratively, via literature review and background research to map the landscape, broad-ranging expert interviews (n = 6) to map out the broad problem space, an expert workshop (see workshop agenda in the Appendix) attended by 14 experts on peer review and OPR, which was preceded by a questionnaire to collect, synthesise and validate best-practices on OPR implementation and to discuss the possibilities for future collaboration to deepen research into OPR. Publishers represented in the workshop include F1000, Publons, Nature, Taylor & Francis, Hindawi, Elsevier, BMC, PLOS, MDPI, eLife, Royal Society Open Science, BMJ, Copernicus Publications, Wiley.

We have seen that the variety of innovations that come under the umbrella term “open peer review” can be combined in a multitude of ways. The differing kinds of OPR have a lot of potential to improve peer review, but it is clear that no one model will fit all disciplines or overcomes all obstacles. Which of these are best, in which circumstances, and for which communities? What is their effect upon factors like review quality, the time the process takes, incentivising researchers to review (or not), the participation of traditionally under-represented groups, or (in open identities) the risks of negative consequences for especially early-career researchers from more senior colleagues whose work they negatively review? The fact is, as a recent systematic review of the available evidence makes clear, none of these questions can be currently answered authoritatively with hard evidence (Ross-Hellauer, 2017). Peer review, as the basis for scientific quality assurance should itself rest firmly on a scientific footing. Scholarship should take peer review seriously as an object of study. It is too central to the shaping and validation of scientific knowledge to rely too heavily on mere anecdote and intuition. As an important recent study by Grimaldo, Marušić and Squazzoni of the scientific literature on peer review shows (2018), although research on that subject has been growing in recent years, to date “despite its central role in research, peer review has been examined only through small-scale research projects”. In the assessment of the authors, “there is need to encourage collaboration and knowledge sharing across different research communities”. It can be argued that more research would be able to be fostered if we were able to open all suitably anonymised information about peer review, via open datasets according to shared standards, to the wider community of scholars to maximise research. Here, journals with OPR processes have a key advantage, since so much more of the peer review process is already, by its nature, public.

²⁵ Ross-Hellauer, T. (2018)

²⁶ Ross-Hellauer, T. (2018)

As pertains to OPR, the need for data-sharing to foster research and hence evidence-based innovation in peer review is especially acute. OPR is an umbrella term for a cluster of innovative methods with far-reaching impact upon the peer review process, but whose full consequences are often obscure.

The need for more evidence into the efficacy of OPR

Our cohort of experts universally saw the need for more research into the efficacy of OPR. It was felt that in general, further research is needed into peer review as a whole, with a lack of knowledge of the contribution peer review makes to the scientific process. Among the key reasons given for the need for more research into OPR specifically, it was stated that decision-making should be data-driven, and respondents reported concerns that there is a lack of systematic analysis on the impact of various forms of OPR on the quality of peer review processes, with arguments for or against OPR often based on political or philosophical preconceptions rather than on data about its efficacy. This was attributed to the limited availability of datasets, restricted to only a few publishers. One respondent advised they felt that even some of the studies on open peer review that have been done should not be relied upon too heavily, owing to poor generalisability, weak study design or the age of the studies in a shifting landscape. Even those convinced by the studies already available acknowledged that more data/studies would be key in persuading others (especially in fields where OPR is less established) of the efficacy and advantages of OPR. In general, although attitudes to OPR have been more widely studied than actual practice, here too, more evidence is needed on how different disciplines react to OPR. These questions extend beyond mere efficacy to peer review's place in the broader culture of research – it was felt that there is a lack of understanding of the influence of contexts and academic hierarchy and power on attitudes towards OPR and open review methods.

All except two respondents indicated that their organisations would be interested in collaborating in the development of a programme of data-sharing and research into the efficacy of OPR. Those who indicated otherwise advised this was, in one case, because the respondent was from a research institution more focused on education and teaching, and in the other case because they had already shared data, including data about OPR, via the PEERE data sharing protocol²⁷, but that this initiative could and should be able to access such data through PEERE. In the event, it seems this is not the case, as access to the PEERE data is still limited only to members of that COST action at present (although PEERE are working on enabling greater access).

Barriers to data-sharing

Having established that there was a need to foster greater data-sharing, and the will amongst organisations to do so, we moved on to address the barriers our respondents could see to such an initiative. Our respondents highlighted the following issues:

- **Data confidentiality:** There will need to be an adequate framework data release agreement and mechanisms for data confidentiality. Open data should be suitably anonymised where necessary. Data which cannot be made open should be made available only to permitted third parties.
- **Data ownership:** Publishers do not own all the data that might be shared. Review reports usually remain the intellectual property of reviewers, for example (conditions are usually set by publishers). Where open reports have been published under open licenses, sharing should not be an issue. But for closed reviews, data-sharing will be problematic and may require reviewer agreement (although mechanisms such as that which the medical community use to manage data could be used). Finally, not all journal data is owned by the publisher – where the publisher only runs the journal (e.g., for a scholarly society) there would be a need to secure approval from societies and editors for journals the publisher does not own.
- **Stakeholder approval:** Even where the data is owned by the publisher or society consenting to share, the initiative would be advised to secure agreement of editorial boards, communities and reviewers.

²⁷ <http://www.peere.org/2016/12/30/the-peere-data-sharing-protocol/>

- **Time, effort, costs:** Publishers are also naturally wary of the amount of work and commitment that might be involved. For example, the costs of identifying, collating, cleaning, anonymizing, harmonizing and curating data. Some reports, particularly manuscript-level cross-journal reports for titles using off-the-shelf manuscript submission systems, can have hefty costs.
- **Reputational risk:** Reticence might also come from concerns amongst publishers and scholarly societies about the risk to reputation that could stem from opening up such data to wider scrutiny – they may be wary of standing out as performing poorly in some respect, for example. As one participant bluntly noted, if sharing data stands to hurt publishers, participation will be affected. For this reason, it was suggested that information such as review times, number of invitations, number declined, etc., could be aggregated or anonymised so as not to identify individual journals. In practice such steps might hurt the transparency and reproducibility of any subsequent studies which use that data. Here critical mass might be needed - if most publishers were to engage then others would likely follow.
- **Enabling meaningful comparisons:** There would be a need to ensure that data from different journals can be meaningfully compared. The variety of different peer review models would make it difficult to compare like with like. This would be better enabled by defining specific data-fields and documenting any idiosyncrasies which might make comparison difficult.

Varieties of data that could be shared

We next moved on to consider the varieties of data that it would be possible to usefully make either (1) open data (suitably anonymised where necessary), or (2) closed but FAIR (with restrictions on access and suitable processes to ensure confidentiality).

Open data

Respondents agreed that the following types of data could be usefully opened **for OPR journals**, where the OPR process was such that this information was already public, or where releasing such information would not breach existing agreements or norms of confidentiality. Such information could include type of peer review process at the relevant journal, names of reviewers, demographics of reviewers (country, gender, institution), review word-count, full texts of reviews (if PR model includes open reports), and information related to the editorial processes, such as name of editor, number of invitations, assigned reviewers and completed reviews per submission, number of rounds of review.

Restricted access data

For restricted data (whether for OPR or traditional peer review journals), it was agreed that given sufficient confidentiality guarantees, all the above information could also be in principle subject to sharing. The additional data could also be made available under specific conditions, such as confidential letter to the editor, triage documentation, the publisher business model allowed, reviewer recommendation.

Prioritising research questions

We next asked our experts what they thought are the most important areas in which more evidence is needed with regard to the different elements of open peer review, and which specific research questions they would like to see addressed. From the perspective of the publishers the questions with high priority related to the process and costs OPR's implementation. From the perspective of the research the questions were prioritized to what would be most valuable to learn from the perspective of inclusion, participation and transparency in research.

Next steps

From this analysis it is clear that publishers and others see the need for more research into OPR, are open to the idea of data-sharing to foster this, but see some concrete barriers to implementation in questions of ownership and confidentiality of some data, the need to gain stakeholder approval, the degree of effort and costs that might

be involved in participating, risks to reputation, and the need to collect, structure and document data in such a way as to enable meaningful comparisons. With this landscape made clearer, we can map a way ahead.

- **Define agenda and research priorities:** From the foregoing, it is clear that publishers often remain the gatekeepers of information regarding peer review processes. Concerns about reputational risk and potential costs in terms of time and effort are powerful barriers against participation in such an initiative. Hence, it seems publishers – even though interested in participating – may not immediately be ready to open all varieties of data possible. As a first step, it was suggested by respondents that one or two key priority questions could be selected and publishers invited to contribute data. A central repository of data could be collected (perhaps as a Zenodo community), linked to a registry of key research questions. This would have the advantage of demonstrating value while targeting key research questions, and acting as a proof-of-concept.
- **Incentivizing research:** Once data has been collected and made available (either as open data or with restricted access), there remains the question of how to incentivize research that utilises that data. It was suggested that research could be incentivized via a hackathon linked to a journal special issue (the Open Access journal Publications, of which the primary author of this study is Editor-in-Chief, would be a potential venue).
- **Coordination:** The value of OpenUP coordinating this activity, as a third-party organisation distanced from publishers, was noted by a few participants. To further formalise the initiative, it was suggested that it could formally be convened as an interest or working group via the Research Data Alliance.
- **Foster cultural change:** It is currently widely culturally accepted that peer review processes are largely a black-box of proprietary information, and that publishers can act as gate-keepers of this information, allowing access to researchers as they wish. As said above, it can be said that the duty of care that publishers have to participants in their processes, as well as to scholarship itself, mean that this should not be considered so clear-cut. The Open Science agenda presses the need for ever greater transparency and accountability on researchers and research institutions – should the same principles not extend to those overseeing quality assurance processes? Funders and institutions could support such initiatives by explicit statements of support for such transparency, or even by making transparency on journal processes a key condition for eligibility for reimbursement of APCs or journal subscriptions.

4.2 Guidelines for implementing open peer review

OPR is a diverse cluster of interrelated but distinct innovations, which can be combined in a myriad of combinations that fall under this term. Hence any publisher wishing to move in this direction faces crucial choices about which elements of openness to embrace, and these decisions will in their turn expose them to potential advantages and disadvantages for the quality of their peer review systems. Issues of which OPR system is optimal, for which communities and in which circumstances have to be considered when moving towards a more transparent review system within publishing.

The guidelines for implementing OPR are based on background research, expert interviews and an expert synthesis/validation workshop. The workshop included several publishers²⁸ with different experiences with open peer review processes: employing post-publication peer review, interactive or collaborative peer review, or some leading experiments or initiatives with open peer review involving a small sample of journals. Therefore, inputs reflected varied knowledge and perspectives on why and how to implement a more transparent review system. Although the advice is directed mainly at editors and publishers of scientific journals, since this is the area in

²⁸ Workshop participants included F1000, Publons, Nature, Taylor & Francis, Hindawi, Elsevier, BMC, PLOS, MDPI, eLife, Royal Society Open Science, BMJ, Copernicus Publications, Wiley

which OPR is at its most mature, many of the principles may also be applicable for the implementation of OPR in other areas (e.g., books, conference submissions, grants).

General advise

1. Do your homework

Study existing models and OPR implementations through publisher websites, published literature, presentations and online resources. Use industry contacts and discussion platforms to discuss and learn lessons from publishers and journals who have already implemented OPR procedures. Examine which particular aspects of your peer review process you would like to improve – for example transparency, participation, speed – and choose the elements of the process to open based on this.

2. Listen to your research communities

Next, engage journal communities – firstly by consulting your editorial board and reviewers to get them on board with the idea. A committed and engaged Editor who can drive such discussions will really help. Find keen researchers to work with and gauge interest in model among communities the journal serves. Let their reviewers, authors and readers know in advance, and if you are unsure of how such developments might be received, consider announce plans in a journal editorial and seek community feedback. Consider starting with particular disciplines that are more open to experiment with OPR, especially those where other journals in the field already use OPR.

3. Be pragmatic in your approach

Your communities may be more receptive to some elements than others, and so prioritising the areas you would like to change and being prepared to compromise from the ideal situation or at least take a phased approach may help you maintain traction and community buy-in. It will also make it easier to systematically assess the success or otherwise of any particular innovation. Another option would be to make elements you would like to introduce optional. In that case, it would still be possible to signal your support for this innovation by making it the default option and inviting reviewers or authors to opt out

4. Get the technology right

A deciding factor in prioritising the elements of openness to include will be the technical possibilities of your system. Whether you are a small publisher using open source software or a large publisher which uses one of the major manuscript handling services, if your electronic editorial office and production/publication systems and workflows cannot currently be easily configured for OPR elements, they may be expensive to implement. You have to consider the potential costs and human resource requirements to fund system developments.

5. Sell the concept

Once you have decided on the model you'd like to move to, you have your communities on board, and have prioritised which OPR elements to implement, you'll still need to sell the concept the communities. As a general strategy, you should engage with the research community to find academics who are enthusiastic about OPR to be “open champions” in advocating to their peers. It is important to be aware that communication is key and terminology is important.

6. Watch out for pitfalls

As the stewards of the peer review process, publishers and editors have a duty of care to ensure reviewers and authors fully understand the systems of peer review in which they participate, and its potential advantages and disadvantages. Misunderstandings could derail processes.

Researchers often have strong feelings about OPR, and not all are positive. Ensuring dialogue with your journal communities in advance will help garner support for the process.

Trait-specific advice

1. Open identities

Whether or not to open reviewer identities is a huge question. Reviews with open identities can seem to be more constructive in tone but there is some anecdotal evidence that finding reviewers to review openly might be more difficult (although other publishers have reported having no such problems). If you opt for open identities, therefore, it would be advisable to create a standard reviewer invitation email which includes a clear description of the open identities review process and its potential advantages as well as disadvantages, as well as a standard follow-up text which goes deeper into these issues to convince those who are reticent. If you are keen to invite a specific person who is reticent, be ready to negotiate to persuade them (e.g., by offering more time to review).

If you are interested but not ready to fully commit to open identities, you could start small with a pilot and scale up. Alternatively, you could allow reviewers to opt in or out. To signal the journal's support for the concept but allow reviewers choice, you could make open identities the default but enable reviewers to opt out of the process. Another possibility would be to maintain a standard single- or double-blind review process but to publish reviewer names alongside the final article. In any case, wherever reviewer names are disclosed along with publication, be sure to use identifiers (e.g., ORCID) to link that activity to reviewer profiles and further enable credit and career evaluation. A further issue to consider is whether the identity of the handling editor(s) should also be open. After all, at journals with very high desk rejection rates, editorial selection is also a form of peer review.

2. Open reports

Open reports peer review is where review reports (either full reports or summaries) are published alongside the relevant article. Often, although not in all cases (e.g., EMBO reports, <http://embor.embopress.org>), review names are published alongside the reports. The main benefits of this measure lie in making currently invisible but potentially useful scholarly information available for re-use. There is increased transparency and accountability that comes with being able to examine normally behind-the-scenes discussions and processes of improvement and assessment, and a potential to further incentivize peer reviewers by making their peer review work a more visible part of their scholarly activities (thus enabling reputational credit).

The technical requirements for publishing review reports should be considered. Best practice is to assign individual DOIs to reports. In this way, review reports become a citeable, discoverable and creditable part of the scholarly record in their own right. To facilitate this process, Crossref has been developing a schema for review report metadata (Hendricks, 2017).

3. Open Participation, Pre-review Manuscripts & Open Final Version Commenting

Open participation peer review allows the wider community to contribute to the review process. This can be either during publication (by making a pre-review manuscript openly available online as a pre-print or discussion paper) or after publication (by enabling comments on the publisher website or via a third-party platform like PubPeer). Whereas in traditional review, editors identify and invite specific parties (peers) to review, open participation processes invite interested members of the scholarly community to participate in the review process, either by contributing full, structured reviews or shorter comments. Crowdsourcing reviewers in this way in theory ensures that fields do not become too insular or self-referential, enabling cross-disciplinary perspectives and potentially increase the number of researchers who can contribute to the quality assurance of manuscripts.

A key decision here is whether to make comments open to anybody (anonymous or registered), or whether to require some credentials before allowing comments. Various options are available depending on your own communities. At Copernicus, for example, reviewers can be anonymous but open commentators on discussion papers must add their identities. However, although MDPI's Preprints service originally allowed only registered users to comment, this condition was recently relaxed. Despite concerns that this would lead to a lower-quality of comments, MDPI in fact reports having had few problems so far.

A further crucial issue is that open participation processes often experience low-uptake. is often used as a complement to a parallel process of solicited peer review. At the open access journal Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics (ACP), which publishes pre-review discussion papers for community comments, only about one in five papers is commented upon (Pöschl, 2012). Hence, open participation review is arguably better seen as a complement to, rather than a replacement for, invited peer review. In any case, some mediation of the community will help to stimulate engagement.

4. Open interaction

Open interaction peer review allows and encourages direct reciprocal discussion between reviewers, and/or between author(s) and reviewers. In traditional peer review, reviewers and authors correspond only with editors. Reviewers have no contact with other reviewers, and authors usually have no opportunity to directly question or respond to reviewers' comments. Allowing interaction amongst reviewers or between authors and reviewers, or between reviewers themselves, is another way to “open up” the review process, enabling editors and reviewers to work with authors to improve their manuscript. Examples of journals which enable pre-publication interaction between reviewers are the *EMBO Journal* and *eLife*. *Frontiers* has gone a step further, including an interactive collaboration stage with dialogue between authors, reviewers and editor(s).

While this extended dialogue might be expected to increase the editorial workload in some parts of the process, publishers practicing such methods actually report that they can also reduce workload in other parts. For example, the *eLife* consultation approach involves more work upfront (i.e. the consultation process and the drafting of the consensus decision letter), but time is saved later on if the editor decides on the revised version rather than sending back to the referees.

5. Open platforms

As identified above, small-scale piloting of OPR processes is often made difficult by the fact that existing publication systems are not yet configured for OPR. In this case, publishers may resort to work-arounds, but the sub-optimal nature of the technology may then become an inhibiting factor in the success of the experiment. One solution here would be for a third-party OPR platform to offer their service as a plug-in to existing workflows for conducting such experiments.

4.3 Training and motivation

Scholars, especially at an early stage of their academic advancement, are often confronted with many difficulties and questions related to the evaluation and publishing of their work. It is therefore essential to offer them the necessary theoretical and practical knowledge, which will guide them through the “publishing jungle” (Boile, 2016).

Training programs are essential for reviewers regardless of the review methodology they are involved in (traditional or open peer review) for several reasons:

1. training should define core competencies for reviewers,

2. training should be tailored to ensure reviewers and editors to meet some basic discipline specific standards.

Courses on peer review should provide basic training, certification and continuing education in order to have a long-lasting impact in improving review practices. Trainings can contribute to employing good principles (e.g. COPE²⁹) as standards for all academic review processes. Publishers can enable the developments of review standards and display major milestones at their journals website in order to ensure their wide uptake among researchers.

Trainings can take several different formats: workshops and face-to-face trainings, web-based and self-taught packages, as well as mentoring. However, research on the outcomes of these trainings does not report effective results. A study by Callaham et al. (2007), examining medical evaluation processes, says that without a better understanding of the basic skills of reviewing, it seems unlikely journals and editors will be successful in systematically improving their selection of reviewers. Regarding the methodologies, trainings can address a wide audience if they are online, apply elements of adult learning and allow for self-paced learning.

OpenUP takes on the task not only of identifying training solutions for researchers that provide practical guidance to better understand the peer review mechanisms and processes, but also offers training sessions for young scholars and interested stakeholders. Therefore, this section of the study has a double purpose: (1) gathering information on trainings offered by publishers and other review services for researchers to improve their skills as reviewers, and (2) describing the results of the OpenUP training workshops.

4.3.1 Trainings for reviewers

Publons

Publons offers a full service for reviewers. Within the framework of the Publons Academy, free, on-demand courses are offered, which not only teach researchers the core competencies of peer reviewing, but also connect them with journal editors to practice their newly acquired skills³⁰. Benefits of enrolling in this peer review training also include practicing writing real post-publication reviews, creating a reviewer profile on Publons, improving writing and publishing skills in general.

Based on the advice of an expert panel of researchers, who not only have a wide experience of reviewing for numerous journals, but also sat on editorial boards, Publons put together an easy to follow 12 steps to take to ensure a thorough and robust review. The list includes recommendations on how to prepare for the review, tips on how to read the manuscript critically, advice on common research flaws to watch out for and on how to compile reviewer's response for revisions (Wilkinson, 2017).

Publishers

Wiley created a toolbox³¹ for reviewers. They provide access to a series of short videos, which either offer basic information and some guidelines on the review process in an animated fashion, or share experiences of reviewers and editors in short question and answer format.

²⁹ https://publicationethics.org/files/Ethical_Guidelines_For_Peer_Reviewers_2.pdf

³⁰ <https://publons.com/blog/publons-academy/>

³¹ <https://authorservices.wiley.com/Reviewers/journal-reviewers/becoming-a-reviewer.html/peer-review-training.html>

Wolters Kluwer Author Services employs Editage³² (a service of a global medical communication agency) to provide authors with a range of editorial and educational services with the aim of helping authors with manuscript preparation for publication in professional medical, nursing, and allied health journals. They also offer a course for reviewers including valuable advice from learned academics who have decades of experience as peer reviewers. Apart from the basics of peer reviewing, perspectives are shared with reviewers on how expert research methodologists and statisticians approach peer reviews.

Elsevier offers a series of modules on its website³³ which, besides the know-how tips, deal with the motivations behind peer reviewing. The videos explain why it is so important to get involved in peer review and the many benefits it can bring including how carrying out peer review can sharpen writing skills and getting involved in the review process can also mean an introduction to experts in the field. The course also explains why there is a move towards making peer review more transparent.

ACS Reviewer Lab™ also provides free peer-review training course providing guidance on how to deal with ethical situations, identifying core criteria for evaluating manuscripts, and offering tips how to write a first-rate review³⁴.

The Genetics Society has developed a pilot program³⁵ for GSA member graduate students, postdoctoral fellows, and junior faculty to serve as peer-reviewers for the journal. The purpose of the program, besides providing training on the principles, purposes, and best practices of peer-review, as well as guidelines and models for fair reviews that are helpful to both the authors and the editors, is to incentivize young researchers to participate in the review process. According to the program description, peer reviewers gain skills to communicate specialist information in an accessible way, to give feedback that is constructive and fair, and besides how they can contribute to the discipline, they also learn hard-to-show “soft” skills like workplace etiquette, knowing when to seek advice, time management, and reliably meeting deadlines.

Copernicus Publications contribute to face-to-face trainings on peer review in the format of workshops. At the annual General Assembly of the European Geosciences Union³⁶ the editors of the publishing house are asked to participate in and provide input to workshops which aim to offer the research community (in particular early career scientists) with a better understanding of open access and open review processes. At these events peer-review experts share their experiences with open science methods and tools and provide examples that the audience can give feedback on and discuss.

Summary

All these program and courses describe peer reviewing as a complex set of skills which require not only scientific knowledge of a field, but also skills and experience with managing ethical issues, managing workflows and communicating with peers in a research community. Considering the overload reviewers experience within the current publishing system and the difficulty publishers face to find competent reviewers, these courses also function as motivational tools to highlight the benefits of being a reviewer.

³² <https://www.editage.com/>

³³ <https://researcheracademy.elsevier.com/navigating-peer-review/fundamentals-peer-review>

³⁴ <https://www.acsreviewerlab.org/>

³⁵ http://www.genetics-gsa.org/careers/training_program.shtml

³⁶ <https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2018/session/28985>

4.3.2 OpenUP training workshop

The OpenUP project tasks also include training activities both in the form of organizing training workshops and preparing and dissemination training materials through the OpenUPhub.

A joined training event of OpenUP and FOSTER was organized on June 20, 2018 in Göttingen (see Agenda in the Appendix). The workshop had several foci of discussion: (1) the changing discourse of peer review, (2) the strengthening presence of open peer review in scholarly publishing, and (3) the emerging methods and tools in support of open scholarship. The workshop was planned to provide young researchers with information about the methods and tools of open scholarship, open peer review in particular, and how they strengthen core principles of research integrity. It also wished to engage a wider research community in a dialogue about open peer review and some of the major aspects of the transforming scholarly publishing system (demand for greater transparency, erosion of incentives, lack of training).

The workshop was divided into three parts, each highlighting different aspects of open peer review. While the first part concentrated on the basic principles and notions, advancing an understanding of the benefits and potential drawbacks of open peer review (OPR) and discussing different perspectives on advantages and disadvantages of openness, the second session offered a more in-depth examination of the issues related to transparent evaluation processes, such as increasing reliability and incentives, data sharing and data availability and training for reviewers. The panel discussion at the end of the workshop, involving invited experts from different disciplines, focused on best practices and good examples of data sharing and transparent review and research practices with the aim of outlining the direction the open science movement could take in different fields of study.

The training incorporated different types of exercises. Role playing was employed to discuss advantages and disadvantages of openness from the perspectives of key stakeholders (author, reviewer, researcher/reader), and small group discussion was chosen to examine various attributes affecting open identities, reports and open participation (skills, knowledge, awareness, experience and mind set). The more in-depth look at OPR involved group discussions on three chosen issues moderated by the invited topic experts and workshop organisers. Groups were supplied with a template to record discussion points on examples of good practice, barriers and challenges to implementation, and (based on these barriers) what actions should be taken, by whom. Groups then rotated so that each group moved on to evaluate and validate the findings of the other groups.

The outcomes of discussion provided rich information on how transparency and openness in the review process can be increased from different disciplinary perspectives. The results basically reflect on what issues trainings on open peer review should focus on to ensure wider uptake of transparent review practices and increased willingness to participate in the process among younger researchers. Some of the main conclusive points include recommendations how to enhance openness in regard to specific attributes of OPR, such as open identity, open report and open participation.

To enhance open identities/reports/participation in the peer review process attention should be focused on the following issues:

increasing **awareness** of:

- credits for review,
- project results like OpenUP and FOSTER reporting on developments in scholarly publishing discourse and offering training materials,
- education opportunities at graduate level,
- standards of reuse,

- tools to enhance visibility and citability,
- building communities,

change of mind-set on:

- reviewing should be considered as a scientific output,
- accepting transparency by wider disciplines and journals,
- have willingness to share comments,
- advance helpful attitude toward openness in general,
- becoming more proactive.

training on peer review:

- focus on skills highlighting the three ‘C’s: be constructive, critical and civil,
- policies,
- scientific context of review (expertise in the field).

acquiring skills to:

- communicate with fellow researchers,
- navigate and use new platforms and tools,

obtaining experience with:

- mentoring and training,
- formulating free text,

user friendly resources:

- one platform instead of fragmented publishing and dissemination system,
- code of conduct accepted by communities,
- moderation to help communication and commenting process.

Workshop participants also collected ideas on what reviewer training should focus on. Good examples of training opportunities included journal clubs as forums where review comments are posted and openly available to learn from them, or the evaluation process of evaluators where authors indicate the helpfulness of the reviews provided, or templates and structured scoring help beginner reviewers focus their attention on specific aspects of evaluation. Workshops and courses offered at major scientific conferences were also brought up as good opportunities for reviewer trainings.

Information about the challenges were also gathered, which are needed to be overcome in order to ensure wider participation in the peer review process. These barriers included the lack of awareness among young researchers on how and why to get involved in the process, the lack of knowledge about the latest developments in the field of scholarly publishing, and the lack of formal training of peer review. Participants recommended both bottom-up actions from the communities to achieve large-scale, proactive involvement, and also top-down actions receiving clear guidelines from academic societies, graduate schools, and managing reviewer misconduct through introducing anti-harassment policies and committees established by organizations.

The conclusive thoughts on peer review training also indicate how participation in the review process could be incentivized across disciplines:

- increase awareness of developments in the scholarly publishing system, changing review policies and standards,
- advance change of perspectives on how peer review is valued on institutional level (receiving credit for review activity) and on how transparency increases acknowledgement for the review work,
- promote training on variety of skills on how to conduct good review and how to communicate with fellow researchers, and on how to become more proactive as an author and reviewer.

5. Conclusion

Common challenges in peer review

OpenUP findings and final thoughts on the future development of the scholarly peer review system resonate with the conclusions from the Eighth International Congress on Peer Review and Scientific Publication (2017)³⁷: Although the conference recommendations refer to the scholarly peer review systems in general, several of the conclusions are relevant to the development of open peer review methodologies, as well. From the list of 15 things the conference identifies as takeaways to think about, there are several issues which can be related to the challenges we identified in relation to open peer review:

1. **Peer review is important.** It is a significant element of the scholarly communication process ensuring quality control, improving scientific knowledge by enhancing the disseminated outputs to become a concise, clear and credible piece of work. Workshop results indicate that the primary barrier behind the slow uptake in dissemination alternatives other than journal publishing (preprint posting, repository deposit) is the lack of a structured peer review system connected to them.

2. There is a demand for **evidence-based research** on open peer review: decision-making on the implementation of peer review alternative methodologies should be based on data-driven, and respondents reported concerns, however there is a lack of systematic analysis on the impact of various forms of OPR and on the quality of peer review processes. Due to the limited availability of datasets, restricted to only a few publishers, these types of research could be integrated into the scholarly communication processes if access to these data sets were granted and researchers were motivated to use them.

3. Enhancing **proactivity of authors and reviewers**: Authors are one of the key stakeholders in the publishing workflow. It is important to consider their needs in the continuously transforming communication system. As the requirements for increased transparency and openness in dissemination are being negotiated among the research communities (due to funder mandates, changing disciplinary practices, etc.), authors' preferences for peer review types are changing, as well. Authors should be educated about journal policies, licencing issues, publishing and peer review alternatives, enabling them to make conscious decisions where to publish under what conditions. Reviewers, on the other hand, need to get information about the peer review policy of the journals, the licences connected to publishing the review reports. Therefore, they have to make conscious choices for which publishing venues and under what conditions they accept review requests.

4. **Journal editors** play a central role in academic publishing: their manifold tasks include planning forthcoming issues, finding peer reviewers, and mediating the review process. They are also key figures in implementing open science practices in the journal publication system. While the journal's reputation is based on the quality of the peer review process and the quality of the editorial board, the editor is considered the main contact person and the leader of the journal. Editors are influential opinion leaders within the related research communities, thus they are integral elements in the implementation process of alternative peer review methodologies.

5. Focus on **incentives to review**: there is a shortage of peer reviewers. As the amount of journal submissions is continuously on the rise, journal editors struggle to find reliable and willing peer reviewers. It is mainly due to two primary reasons: (1) young scholars are reluctant to get involved in peer review due to the lack of training and mentoring, and (2) researchers with work overloads are not motivated to take on extra scholarly tasks. Peer review activities are generally not included in academic evaluations and acknowledgement for review work is

³⁷<https://www.editage.com/insights/sites/default/files/An%20overview%20of%20the%20Eighth%20International%20Congress%20on%20Peer%20Review%20and%20Scientific%20Publication.pdf>

only available through individual journals (void of subscription fees or decreased APC charges) or independent review services (Publons).

6. **Peer reviewer training** is highly discussed issue in scholarly communication: training is needed to educate the future generation of reviewers and to increase the number of reviewers available. However, structured training programs for reviewers – such as those offered by Publons, Editage, ACS, and Nature – are fairly recent, there is not enough evidence yet to see whether trainings help in incentivizing future participation, or they positively influence the quality of reviews. Based on the feedback we gathered in our workshops, trainings on open science methodologies, tool and services should be incorporated into the regular research communication and educational practices.

7. **Guidelines and best practices:** pilot studies and experiments with alternative review methodologies conducted by publishing platforms and journals provide valuable information both on good practices and the challenges that might occur in implementing open science tools and workflows. A success story within a small field of study can affect the research and communication practices of other disciplines. Furthermore, guidelines and recommendations resulting from pilot initiatives or project research, such as OpenUP, may contribute to the development of standards for the implementation of review alternatives in the scholarly publishing process.

8. **Awareness** is key: the increasing uptake of open science practices will be the result of effective awareness raising among researchers and university leaders. Changes in the way scientific research is being conducted, accessed and utilised by scientists and society at large come from bottom up, from the roots of scientific activities and scholarly communication. Top down requirements, guidelines and recommendation might provide the direction of transformations, but Open Science practices will gain momentum when considerable number of researchers will support the system. To this end, raising awareness on the benefits of these practices, on the know-how of implementing and using the new services and tools, on the rights and requirements of all stakeholders involved in the transforming scholarly system is indispensable in the process towards a more open, fair, transparent and sustainable scientific eco-system.

Future directions

OpenUP is dedicated to continuing the work in identifying new developments in the scholarly peer review discourse and contributing to increasing uptake of alternative peer review tools and services. OpenUP is participating in several initiatives which aim to transform the scholarly communication system.

Transpose³⁸ is a new, grassroots initiative aiming to crowdsource a list of journal policies for (1) open peer review, (2) co-reviewer involvement, and (3) pre-printing. The work tasks include the examination of the following concrete issues:

- **Preprints:** on the one hand, researchers need a clear understanding of journal policies regarding the acceptability of preprints, both as submissions and citations, and on the other hand, policies with clear guidelines should help authors in their dissemination practices with regard of preprint posting and journal submissions.
- **Unacknowledged reviewing:** Early career researchers (namely graduate students and postdocs) may feel hesitant to contribute to peer review done in the name of their supervisor; and supervisors may not disclose names of others involved in review where journal policies suggest such common practices may

³⁸ <https://transpose-publishing.github.io/>

have punitive consequences. Providing appropriate and ethical credit for their involvement would reduce their risk.

- **Extent of open peer review procedures:** survey results show a wide support among researchers for posting peer review reports, however there are only a few journals practicing open report reviews. Tracking these practices in one place over time will allow editors and publishers to reconsider practices to match those of their peers.
- **Data-sharing on journal processes:** in order to advance a more evidence-based research on peer review, data collected by publishers about the review processes should be made available to more systematically test how these innovations affect the quality and efficiency of scholarly communications.

These goals correspond with the OpenUP objectives, therefore participating in this initiative will ensure the continuation of our work regarding open peer review and alternative dissemination even after the end of our project period.

OpenUP is dedicated to continuing raising awareness on OPR and providing information to all stakeholders about peer review alternatives through the OpenUPhub³⁹ and through participating in webinars and training workshops. OpenUP has also contributed to the development of the OPR training program by the FOSTER project. The training program introduces participants to open peer review workflows and offers a know-how to write a constructive and responsible open peer review⁴⁰.

Furthermore, OpenUP is supporting the Open Science MOOC⁴¹ initiative, which was established as a response to the European Commission's report "Providing researchers with the skills and competencies they need to practise Open Science"⁴². This initiative supports the importance to inform, educate and support researchers to gain the necessary skills for successfully engage in open science practices.

Involvement in such projects and the OpenUP recommendations for EC policy guidelines on implementing alternative evaluation, dissemination and impact measurement methodologies within the scholarly communication system (D7.2) will contribute to the sustainability of our results and to the advancement a more transparent open science ecosystem.

6. Reference list

Amaral, O. (2018). Comparing quality of reporting between preprints and peer-reviewed articles – a crowdsourced initiative. ASAPbio blog. Retrieved 20 July 2018 from: <http://asapbio.org/amaral-quality>

Ball, P. (2016). Leading mathematician launches arXiv 'overlay' journal. Nature 526, 146 doi:10.1038/nature.2015.18351

Bardi A., Casarosa V., Manghi P., (2017). OpenUP Deliverable D3.2 A specification of the scientific method and scientific communication. <https://osf.io/hvydq/wiki/D3.2/>

Bechhofer S. et al. (2013). Why linked data is not enough for scientists, Future Generation Computer Systems, Volume 29, Issue 2, February 2013, Pages 599-611, ISSN 0167-739X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2011.08.004>.

³⁹ <https://www.openuphub.eu/review>

⁴⁰ <https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/node/2333>

⁴¹ <https://opensciencemooc.github.io/site/>

⁴² https://cdn1.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/policy_library/ec-rtd_os_skills_report_final_complete_2207_1.pdf

- Berg J. et al. (2016) Preprints for the life sciences *Science* vol. 352, issue 6288, pp. 899-901. doi: 10.1126/science.aaf9133
- Boile, M., Sifacaki, E., Toli, E. (2016). Deliverable D2.2 – Training Plan.
- Borgman, C. L. (2015). *Big data, little data, no data: scholarship in the networked world*. MIT press. Retrieved 15 May 2018 from: <https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/big-data-little-data-no-data>
- Borrer, Connie M. (Ed.). (2009). *The Certified Quality Engineer Handbook*. ASQ Quality Press, 321– 332
- Callaham ML & Tercier J. *PLoS medicine* 2007 4(1): e40
- Clarke, M. (2013). Game of Papers: eLife, BMC, PLoS and EMBO Announce New Peer Review Consortium. The Scholarly Kitchen. Retrieved 20 May 2018 from: <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2013/07/15/game-of-papers-elife-bmc-plos-and-embo-announce-new-peer-review-consortium/>
- Davis, P. (2017). Portable Peer Review RIP. The Scholarly Kitchen. Retrieved 20 May 2018 from: <https://scholarlykitchen.sspnet.org/2017/09/25/portable-peer-review-rip/>
- De Roure, D. (2009). Replacing the Paper: The Twelve Rs of the e-Research Record. Open Wetware blog. Retrieved 19 May 2017 from: <http://blog.openwetware.org/deroure/?p=56>.
- Di Leo, A., E. Risi, and L. Biganzoli. (2017). No pain, no gain... What we can learn from a trial reporting negative results. *Annals of Oncology* 28.4: 678-680.
- Enago publishing. (2018). Preprints: Does Publishing Research Early Have a Downside? Retrieved 6 August 2018 from: <https://www.enago.com/academy/preprints-publishing-research-early-downside/>
- European Commission (2015). Validation of the results of the public consultation on Science 2.0: Science in Transition [report]. Brussels: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/consultations/science-2.0/science_2_0_final_report.pdf
- European Commission's Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (RTD) (2016). Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/open-innovation-open-science-open-world-vision-europe>.
- Fresco-Santalla, A. and Hernández-Pérez, T. (2014). Current and evolving models of peer review. *The Serials Librarian*, 67:4, 373-398. doi: 10.1080/0361526X.2014.985415.
- Hendricks, G. and Lin, J. (2017). “Making peer reviews citable, discoverable, and creditable”. Crossref Blog. <https://www.crossref.org/blog/making-peer-reviews-citable-discoverable-and-creditable>
- Grimaldo F, Marušić A, Squazzoni F (2018) ‘Fragments of peer review: A quantitative analysis of the literature (1969-2015)’. *PLoS ONE* 13(2): e0193148. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0193148>
- Görögh, E. et al. (2017). Deliverable D3.1– Practices, evaluation and mapping: Methods, tools and user needs. OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results. Available: http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUP_D3.1_Peer-review-landscape-report-1.pdf
- Görögh, E., Schmidt, B., Banalyte, V. (2018). Open science beyond open access and research data (Workshop 1). ERCEA/A1/PO/2016/06

- Houry, D. et al. (2012). Does mentoring new peer reviewers improve review quality? A randomized trial. *BMC medical education* 12(1): 83.
- King, S. (2017). Peer review: Consultative review is worth the wait. *eLife* 2017;6:e32012
doi: 10.7554/eLife.32012
- Knowledge Exchange Open Scholarship Advisory Group. (2017). Knowledge Exchange approach towards Open Scholarship. Retrieved 20 June 2018 from:
https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/6685/1/KE_APPROACH_TOWARDS_OPEN_SCHOLARSHIP_AUG_2017.pdf
- Luzi, D. and Ruggieri, R. (2018). Pilot 3. Open peer review for research data. Deliverable D6.3 – Final Use Case Evaluation Report.
- McKiernan, et al. (2016) *eLife* 2016,5:e16800 DOI: 10.7554/eLife.16800
- Mehmani, B. (2015). Elsevier trials publishing peer review reports as articles. Elsevier. Retrieved 10 June 2018 from: <https://www.elsevier.com/reviewers-update/story/peer-review/elsevier-pilot-trials-publishing-peer-review-reports-as-articles>
- Mehmani, B. (2016). Is open peer review the way forward? Elsevier. Retrieved 10 June 2018 from: <https://www.elsevier.com/reviewers-update/story/innovation-in-publishing/is-open-peer-review-the-way-forward>
- Mehmani B. (2017). Publishing peer review reports alongside articles with separate DOIs: A pilot study of 5 Journals in different scientific disciplines [version 1; not peer reviewed]. *F1000Research* 2017, 6:1742 (poster) (doi: 10.7490/f1000research.1114918.1)
- Nguyen, V. M., et al. (2015). How Long Is Too Long in Contemporary Peer Review? Perspectives from Authors Publishing in Conservation Biology Journals. *PLoS ONE*, 10(8), e0132557.
<http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0132557>
- Patterson, M. (2018). Peer review: *eLife* trials a new approach. <https://elifesciences.org/inside-elifesciences/2905802e/peer-review-elifesciences-trials-a-new-approach>
- Pöschl, U., (2012) Multi-Stage Open Peer Review: Scientific Evaluation Integrating the Strengths of Traditional Peer Review with the Virtues of Transparency and Self-Regulation. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*, 6(33). doi:10.3389/fncom.2012.00033.
- Prechelt, L. et al. (2014). Elsevier's Reviewer Recognition Platform prepares for next phase. Retrieved 10 June 2018 from: <https://www.elsevier.com/editors-update/story/peer-review/elseviers-reviewer-recognition-platform-prepares-for-next-phase>
- Ross-Hellauer, T. (2017). What is open peer review? A systematic review. *F1000Research*. DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.11369.2
- Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PLoS ONE*, 12(12), e0189311.
<http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>
- Ross-Hellauer, T. (2018) Deliverable 3.3 - Application framework and transformation scenarios for open peer review. OPENing UP new methods, indicators and tools for peer review, impact measurement and dissemination of research results. OpenUP Grant Agreement no. 710722
- Sansone, S. A., et al. (2012). Toward interoperable bioscience data. *Nature genetics*, 44(2), 121-126.
doi:10.1038/ng.1054.

Schroter S et al. Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine 2008 101(10): 507-514.

Shanahan D. (2016). A peerless review? Automating methodological and statistical review, Retrieved 20 May 2017 from: <https://blogs.biomedcentral.com/bmcblog/2016/05/23/peerless-review-automating-methodological-statistical-review/>

Tancock, C. (2018). Innovation in peer review: introducing “volunpeers”. Elsevier. Retrieved 10 June 2018: <https://www.elsevier.com/connect/reviewers-update/innovation-in-peer-review-introducing-volunpeers>

Tennant JP, Dugan JM, Graziotin D et al. (2017). A multi-disciplinary perspective on emergent and future innovations in peer review [version 3; referees: 2 approved]. F1000Research 2017, 6:1151. doi: 10.12688/f1000research.12037.3

Tennant, J. (2018). Peer Review: Preprints and overlay journals. Accessed on Jun2 20, 2018: <http://fossilsandshit.com/15-peer-review-preprints-and-overlay-journals/>

TTOA Consortium. (2018). The Consortium for a Transparent Transition to Open Access (TTOA): A cost-transparent combination of old and new. Public statement. Retrieved 3 July 2018 from: <https://www.fairopenaccess.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/Public-statement-TTOA-consortium-30may18-def.pdf>

Vale, R., Hyman, T. and Polka J. (2018). Peer Feedback. ASAPbio. Accessed on July 10, 2018: <http://asapbio.org/peer-feedback>

Van De Sompel, H.; Rodriguez, M.A. & Bollen, J. (2006) The convergence of digital libraries and the peerreview process. Journal of Information Science, 32(2), pp149-159.

Weintraub, P. G. (2016). The Importance of Publishing Negative Results. Journal of Insect Science, 16(1), 109. <http://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/iew092>

Wilkinson, J. (2017). Writing a peer review is a structured process that can be learned and improved – 12 steps to follow. LSE Impact Blog. Retrieved 7 June 2018 from: <http://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2017/05/17/writing-a-peer-review-is-a-structured-process-that-can-be-learned-and-improved-12-steps-to-follow/>

Zendel, O. (2018). Pilot 1. Open peer review for conferences. Deliverable D6.3 – Final Use Case Evaluation Report.

7. Appendix

7.1. Agenda

Time	Session	Theme
9:30-9:50	1	Welcome session (coffee)
9:50-10:00	2	Introduction to the workshop
10:00-10:30	3	Presentations on FOSTER and OpenUP (introduction to session 4)

10:30-12:00	4	Small group exercises and discussion
12:00-12:30		Lunch
12:30-13:00	5	Presentation by Felix Schönbrodt (introduction to session 6)
13:00-14:30	6	Small group exercise and discussion
14:45-15:45	7	Panel discussion
15:45-16:00	8	Wrap up